

Chemical compounds in PM₁₀ as a tool for source apportionment

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ABSTRACT

Volatile chemical products (VCPs) represent an emerging and under-recognised source of semi-volatile organic compounds in urban air, contributing to the chemical complexity and secondary formation potential of PM₁₀. Despite growing awareness of their role in atmospheric chemistry and exposure, real-world data on VCP-derived species in ambient particles remain scarce. This study provides the first integrated characterisation of VCP-related compounds in PM₁₀ for Central Europe. PM₁₀ samples were collected from Ústí nad Labem, Zdíby, Mělník between November 2022 and April 2023 and analysed using TD-GC/MS. A total of 157 compounds were classified, 106 of which were uniquely associated with product emissions. VCP markers accounted for 0.59–2.11 % of all identified organics, equivalent to 0.05–0.43 µg/m³. Among conventional sources, traffic and biomass burning dominated over coal, while biogenic markers were regionally variable. Plasticisers were pervasive: phthalate esters (PAEs) and non-phthalate plasticisers (NPPs) occurred at most sites. Given EU restrictions on cosmetic PAEs, their ambient levels (ΣPAE 18–54 ng/m³) mainly reflect polymer and plastic emissions rather than personal-care sources. ΣNPP 6–14 ng/m³ were ubiquitous but source-ambiguous; therefore, the ΣNPP/ΣPAE ratio is introduced as a new diagnostic indicator of phthalate substitution, revealing a clear regional gradient (Ústí 2.6 > Mělník 1.1 > Zdíby 0.3). Fragrance-related terpenes showed stronger product than biogenic signatures, and significant fragrance-PAE correlation ($r = 0.67$) indicates functional coupling in emissions. Overall, concentrations were comparable to or below urban levels reported elsewhere, confirming that Central Europe is undergoing an early yet measurable chemical transition in PM₁₀ composition driven by consumer-product and polymer-related emissions.

1. Introduction

The identification of emission sources of particulate matter (PM) is critical for understanding and managing air quality, especially in urban areas (Manisalidis et al., 2020). Particulate matter is a component of airborne aerosols. Particulate matter is a mixture of

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particles of inorganic and organic origin that negatively affect air quality and adversely impact human health (Almeida et al., 2022). PM is associated with many respiratory diseases (Almeida et al., 2022) and cardiovascular diseases; in addition, it is involved in an increase in premature deaths (Gu et al., 2017). Carbonaceous particles (total carbon- TC) consist of organic carbon (OC) and elemental carbon (EC). They form a major fraction of PM and play a central role in atmospheric processes (Amin et al., 2023; Hama et al., 2022). Particles of TC are primarily generated by the incomplete combustion of fossil fuels, biomass, and natural fires, while OC also forms through secondary atmospheric reactions (Skiba et al., 2024). Organic aerosols (OAs) include primary organic aerosols (POAs), emitted directly into the atmosphere, and secondary organic aerosols (SOAs), which are produced by complex multiphase processes in the atmosphere. The mechanisms of SOA formation are among the least understood in atmospheric chemistry (Li et al., 2022). A significant source of SOAs is the production of less volatile products from the oxidation of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) (Li et al., 2024a).

Intermediate-volatility organic compounds (IVOCs) and semi-volatile organic compounds (SVOCs) form an important component of organic aerosol (OA). They can be distributed in the atmosphere between the gaseous and particulate phases (Wernis et al., 2022). The transfer of organic substances between the gaseous and particulate phases occurs either by absorption (diffusion to the volume of the aerosol) or by adsorption (interaction with active surface sites). The distribution mechanisms depend on environmental conditions, in particular, relative humidity (RH), temperature, and aerosol composition (Ahn et al., 2021). Similar approaches combining meteorological parameters with chemical composition analysis using artificial neural networks have been successfully demonstrated by Pongpiachan et al. (2022).

Anthropogenic PM and volatile organic substances (VOCs) come from various sources, including the combustion of coal, biomass, automotive fuels (gasoline, diesel), emissions from industrial processes, and emissions from power plants (Yarwood and Tuite, 2024; Zapletal et al., 2022). VOCs can increase their molecular weight and polarity through oxidation. It brings them into the particle phase (Kulmala et al., 2004). The release of VOCs into the air contributes to air pollution through the formation of particles < 2.5 μm ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$) and SOAs, as well as through ozone generation (Yarwood and Tuite, 2024). Many VOCs are associated with serious health risks and are classified as air toxicants, human carcinogens, and respiratory irritants associated with asthma and other respiratory diseases (Gkatzelis et al., 2021).

Recently, anthropogenic VOCs found in everyday products, collectively referred to as “volatile chemical products” (VCPs), have gained increasing attention because of their significant role in SOA formation and particulate matter formation (Zhou et al., 2024). VCPs include solvents, paints, inks, adhesives, pesticides, cleaning products, and personal care items (Yarwood and Tuite, 2024). Emissions from VCPs, such as reactive monoterpenes, evaporate into the atmosphere and contribute to the formation of SOAs through multiphase reactions (Coggon et al., 2021). Emissions of VCPs (≥ 14 kg per person per year in Pasadena, California) are at least 1.7 times higher than preliminary estimates and significantly increase $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ pollution (Qin et al., 2020). The emissions of VCPs increase with increasing urban population density and significantly impact atmospheric processes (Coggon et al., 2021). As a result, VCPs have become the largest petrochemical source of organic emissions in major US agglomerations (McDonald et al., 2018) such as Los Angeles and New York (Gkatzelis et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2024), and their impact on air quality extends globally (Wang et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2024). The significance of VCP emissions can be illustrated by the US EPA’s 2016 inventory of emissions for the continental U.S., where solvent emissions of 2.6 million tons/year contribute to approximately 20 % of total anthropogenic VOC emissions (Yarwood and Tuite, 2024). More comprehensive studies on the atmospheric processes of secondary organic aerosols from volatile chemical products are necessary, mainly because of their increasing prevalence and critical role in urban air pollution (Zhou et al., 2024).

The emissions of volatile chemical products (VCPs), initially present in the gaseous phase, have become a key focus of the scientific community because of their role in the formation of secondary organic aerosols (SOAs). These aerosols can transition into the particulate phase and contribute to the composition of PM_{10} . However, the origin and behaviour of VCP-related compounds in PM_{10} remain largely unexplored. The present work is the first to address this issue by identifying compounds in PM_{10} that may originate from VCPs and by quantifying their contribution relative to other sources of pollution using a modern TD-GC/MS analytical approach and unique molecular markers.

Although the contribution of VCPs to air pollution has recently gained attention, their role in the composition of particulate matter is still poorly constrained. Most existing studies have focused on gaseous or indoor phases, while systematic data on VCP-related compounds in outdoor PM_{10} are lacking – particularly for Central Europe. Furthermore, few works have simultaneously examined product markers, phthalate and non-phthalate plasticisers, and their interactions with fragrance or solvent constituents. This study bridges these gaps by providing the first integrated characterisation of VCP-derived compounds in PM_{10} across three Central European regions, linking product-related emissions with polymeric and fragrance-derived organics. We also introduce the $\Sigma\text{NPP}/\Sigma\text{PAE}$ ratio as a novel diagnostic indicator of phthalate substitution in ambient air.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sampling

Samples of PM_{10} emissions were taken by ENVITECH Co. on quartz filters with a diameter of 47 mm. Sampling was always carried out for 24 h using the low-volume ENVI LVS1 sampler (ENVITECH Co). The PM_{10} samples were collected on quartz filters in accordance with EN 12341:2023 “Air - Gravimetric standard method for the determination of the mass concentration of suspended particulate matter PM_{10} or $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ ”. The sampling devices were regularly calibrated using standard methods and quality control. All filters were stored and analysed in a controlled environment.

Sampling was carried out at different locations, Ústí nad Labem (Region Ústí), Zdíby and Mělník (all locations in the Region Central

Bohemia) over a period of six months (from November 2022 to April 2023) to capture different spatial conditions (see Fig. 1). A total of 9 samples were collected in Zdíby, 7 in Ústí nad Labem (Ústí), and 15 in Mělník, corresponding to a total of 29 analysed samples (Table S1). In the text, the following abbreviations are used for the respective regions: Zdíby (Z), Ústí nad Labem (U), and Mělník (M). A total of 29 PM₁₀ samples were collected at distinct sites across three regions during a single cold-season campaign, covering diverse urbanisation levels and emission environments. The number and distribution of sites were designed in line with established guidance on spatial representativeness (ITRC, 2013; Kumar, 2009; U.S. EPA, 2013) and recent spatial-optimisation studies showing that networks of roughly 20–30 locations capture most spatial variability in heterogeneous urban settings with > 90 % prediction accuracy (Molla et al., 2022b, 2022a). Accordingly, our 29-site network provides a statistically robust basis for interregional comparison and spatially representative coverage within the campaign period (while not implying temporal representativeness beyond it).

2.2. Description of the area

Mělník is situated 30 km from Prague. It is one of the areas with the highest anthropogenic load in Central Bohemia; the town has 20,000 inhabitants. In 2022, the average annual concentration of PM₁₀ in Kralupy nad Vltavou (15 km SW of Mělník) was 22.2 µg/m³, 16 times exceeding the permitted limit and reaching the maximum measured value of 207 µg/m³ on 26 July (Ecological Centre Kralupy nad Vltavou, 2022). Energy production is concentrated in Mělník. From 2024, the Mělník power plant will have a fluid boiler, a gas boiler room, and an additional source for energy recovery from non-recyclable waste. The petrochemical industry is represented by OMA CZ, a.s., which directly produces its products of auto chemistry, car cosmetics, oils, and greases. Products made of PVC, PE, and PP plastics are manufactured by RETALCzech. Zdíby municipality is situated approximately 9 km north of central Prague; there are approximately 4000 inhabitants. There is no industrial production directly in the municipality.

The Ústí Region lies in northwestern Bohemia and is adjacent to Germany; Ústí itself has approximately 92,000 inhabitants (Czech Statistical Office, 2024). The key industries in Ústí nad Labem are the chemical industry (organic and inorganic chemicals, dyes, and synthetic resins produced by Spolchemie), the production of glycerine by OLEOCHEM Co., and the manufacture of paints and coatings by LABAR s.r.o. Near Ústí nad Labem, there is the Most Coal Basin, where coal is exploited by the Břilina Mine open pit. Brown coal power plants are gradually switching to energy production from other sources, such as gas-fired power plants or biomass boilers. Near the sampling points Ústí nad Labem, the Czech Hydrometeorological Institute (CHMI) stations are situated, where air quality is continuously monitored. In 2022, the average annual concentration of PM₁₀ in the municipality of Stětí (between Mělník and Ústí) was 21.4 µg/m³, and in Ústí nad Labem, it was 20.8 µg/m³ (Czech Hydrometeorological Institute, 2024).

Fig. 1. Map showing the sampled area, including the results of the proportion of identified sources of pollution in PM₁₀; PM₁₀, OC, and EC concentrations for the area of interest, including the number of exceedances of the 24-hour PM₁₀ limit of 50 µg/m³, as defined by Act No. 201/2012 Coll., on Air Protection during the sampling period.

2.3. Methods

2.3.1. Thermo-optical analysis on the EC OC analyser

OC and EC were determined using thermo-optical analysis on the EC OC analyser (manufactured by Sunset Laboratory, Oregon, USA), according to the EN 16909 “Ambient air – Measurement of elemental carbon (EC) and organic carbon (OC) collected on filters”. Determination of OC/EC was carried out using the EUSAAR 2 temperature program with thermo-optical transmission (TOT). Total carbon (TC) is the sum of OC and EC (Monteiro Dos Santos et al., 2016). Before each analysis, a quality check (standardisation) of the apparatus was performed using a sucrose solution of known OC concentration (4.21 µg/µL). A conversion factor of 1.4, commonly reported in the scientific literature (e.g., Bae et al., 2006), was used to convert organic carbon (OC) content to organic matter (OM) content. This factor represents the average ratio between OM and OC and accounts for the average content of other elements, such as hydrogen, oxygen, and nitrogen, in organic compounds.

Given the growing relevance of volatile chemical products (VCPs) in urban air, there is a need to characterise their contribution to PM₁₀. Thermal desorption gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (TD-GC/MS) is a key technique for identifying particulate organic compounds (Flores and Mertoglu, 2020). A fraction of the organic signal remains unresolved. It is reported as undifferentiated organic matter (UOM), and some compounds remain unclassified because their origin cannot be determined (Rushdi et al., 2017).

2.3.2. Thermal desorption – gas chromatography – mass spectrometry

PM₁₀ samples were analysed by thermal desorption–gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (TD-GC/MS; Gerstel, Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany). An internal standard (1,3,5-tri-tert-butylbenzene) was added to each tube before desorption. The thermal-desorption program ramped from 50 °C (1 min hold) to 300 °C (5 min hold) at a rate of 60 °C/min. Desorbed analytes were cryofocused in a cooled injection system (CIS) at –10 °C, rapidly heated to 250 °C (10 °C/s), and transferred to a non-polar HP-5ms capillary column (60 m × 0.25 mm i.d., 0.25 µm film thickness). The GC oven temperature program started at 40 °C (10 min hold), increased at 15 °C/min to 300 °C, and was held for 10 min. Compounds were identified and quantified using mass spectrometry, and data were processed with MassHunter software (Agilent Technologies). Phthalate standards (e.g., DEHP, DBP, DINP) and terpene standards (e.g., limonene, α-pinene, linalool) were used as certified reference materials obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Merck), distributed by Altium International Co., Czech Republic. Multi-point external calibration curves were prepared in the concentration range 0.50–100 mg/L. Each calibration level included the internal standard 1,3,5-tri-tert-butylbenzene at 100 ng/µL. Calibration standards were analysed using the same TD-GC/MS workflow as field samples.

Data evaluation and performance parameters. Quantitative data were processed in MassHunter (Agilent). Figures of merit: linearity, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), accuracy (recovery), and precision (RSD) were evaluated following Eurachem guidelines (Eurachem, 2025).

- Terpenes: linearity $r^2 > 0.999$ for all compounds; LOD= 0.09–0.16 mg/L; LOQ= 0.24–0.37 mg/L; recovery= 82.5–93.0 %; RSD= 4.1–9.3 %.
- Phthalates: linearity $r^2 > 0.999$; LOD= 0.10–0.16 mg/L; LOQ= 0.25–0.31 mg/L; recovery= 80.5–92.0 %; RSD ≤ 10 %.

These results confirm that the analytical procedure provides excellent linearity, low detection limits, and acceptable accuracy and precision, demonstrating that the TD-GC/MS method is fit for quantifying phthalate esters and selected terpenes in PM₁₀ samples.

2.3.3. Source attribution of organic compounds

No receptor modelling (e.g., PMF) was applied; instead, source attribution is literature-informed and database-supported. Traffic, biomass, and coal assignments rely on canonical source profiles (Gentner et al., 2012; May et al., 2014; NRC, 1988; Ružicková et al., 2017; Schauer et al., 1999; U.S. EPA, 2025a, 2025b, 2009), while product/VCP and printing-ink compounds were identified via curated databases (ECHA, 2025; EuPIA, 2023; FSVO, 2023; IFRA, 2024; OECD, 2025; PCPC, 2025) and internal occurrence patterns.

2.4. Statistical analysis

The measured concentrations of individual compounds were compiled into a data matrix, with rows representing compounds and columns corresponding to 29 sampling sites (Zdiby, Ústí nad Labem, Mělník, and additional locations). Empty cells were interpreted as concentrations below the detection limit and were excluded from statistical analyses. To minimise the influence of extreme values that could distort statistical indicators, outliers were removed using the 1.5 × IQR (interquartile range) rule. This robust method is widely applied in environmental data analysis and ensures that only representative concentration values are retained while excluding anomalously high or low measurements. Basic statistical parameters were calculated for each identified compound. Arithmetic mean (AVG), standard deviation (STD), and coefficient of variation (CV) were used to evaluate intra-compound variability and to identify compounds with unstable spatial distributions.

Compounds were subsequently classified according to their spatial significance, based on occurrence frequencies. Globally significant compounds were defined as those detected at 75 per cent or more of all sites, corresponding to a minimum of 22 locations. Thresholds reported in the literature typically range from approximately 50–80 per cent, depending on study objectives; e.g., Li et al. (2023) applied a 50 % threshold, while Liu et al. (2025) used 80 %. In this study, a conservative cutoff of 75 per cent was selected to prioritise consistency across sampling sites. Sensitivity analyses using 75 per cent thresholds are provided in the [Supplementary Information](#). Compounds detected at or above this threshold within a single region (e.g., Zdiby, Ústí nad Labem, or Mělník) were

classified as having local significance. In contrast, compounds exceeding the 75 % detection rate across all 29 sampling sites were designated as globally significant. This dual-tier classification enables differentiation between regionally concentrated emissions and compounds with widespread occurrence throughout the study area.

To identify regionally unique compounds, we applied a dual-criteria approach: (i) occurrence frequency ≥ 75 % within a given site, and (ii) mean concentration at least twice the average background value calculated from the other two locations. This definition reflects spatial enrichment and site-specific dominance, allowing for targeted interpretation of chemical patterns. Although the term “regionally unique compounds” is not universally standardised, similar approaches have been used to distinguish spatially dominant contaminants in environmental matrices (Hilscherová et al., 2009). The applied criteria ensure both statistical robustness and environmental relevance, supporting the identification of compounds with potential regional significance.

Statistical analysis for descriptive statistics and correlation analysis was performed using Origin Pro2019 statistical software. Pearson correlation coefficient at the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ was used for correlation analysis.

The input matrix consisted of the relative contributions (expressed as percentages) of 14 compound groups, classified according to their origin, to the total organic matter in PM₁₀ for each region. Before analysis, the data were standardised using z-score normalisation to ensure comparability across variables. PCA was conducted using the covariance matrix, and the first two principal components (PC1 and PC2) were retained for interpretation, capturing the majority of variance within the dataset.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA), as applied by Pongpiachan et al. (2025a) to investigate structural differences in chemical profiles across sampling locations, was not suitable in our case due to the markedly higher number of analysed compounds compared to the number of sampling sites. Instead, PCA was applied only to support source profile interpretation at the compound group level, based on contributions classified by origin.

3. Results

In the monitored locations of Zdíby, Ústí nad Labem (Ústí), and Mělník, concentrations of suspended particulate matter (PM₁₀) and its organic and carbonaceous components (OM, OC, EC) were analysed (Table S1). The results reveal notable differences in average values and variability across the sites. Zdíby shows the highest average concentrations of organic matter and organic carbon, which may indicate a greater contribution from biogenic emissions or product-related organic sources (Fig. 1). PM₁₀ variability here is moderate. Ústí exhibits the lowest fluctuation in PM₁₀ concentrations, likely reflecting a more homogeneous source profile dominated by combustion and industrial emissions. Average OM and OC levels are the lowest among the three locations. Mělník presents the highest maximum PM₁₀ value and the greatest variability, suggesting episodic pollution sources such as local biomass burning or fluctuating anthropogenic sources. This substantial contribution of organic matter to PM₁₀ is evident across all sites, highlighting the role of both biogenic and anthropogenic sources in shaping atmospheric aerosol composition. The EC and OC concentrations observed in the monitored locations (Mělník, Zdíby, Ústí nad Labem) do not confirm the findings of Schwarz et al. (2019), which reported higher EC concentrations than OC during the winter period, while OC was the dominant component in spring.

3.1. Chemical compounds derived from the combustion of coal, biomass, and transport

The chemical compounds released by biomass combustion are characterised by the presence of anhydrosaccharides, cellulose fission products, and hemicellulose. Anhydrosaccharides are typical markers for emissions from biomass combustion (Simoneit, 1984). A total of 217 compounds that are produced by biomass combustion have been identified (Table S2). The concentrations of compounds from biomass combustion range from 69 to 2716 ng/m³. Using presence thresholds of ≥ 60 % and ≥ 75 %, the regions show distinct patterns in the frequency of biomass-burning compounds. Mělník shows the broadest spectrum at ≥ 60 % (125 compounds), but only 96 remain at ≥ 75 %, indicating less spatial uniformity across sites. Ústí maintains high counts at both thresholds (87 \rightarrow 87), i.e., very consistent occurrence; Zdíby are intermediate (70 \rightarrow 67). After removing anomalies using the $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ rule, arithmetic means and sample SDs were calculated for each region: Zdíby ($n = 8/9$) 151.93 ± 75.30 ng/m³ (CV 49.6 %), Ústí ($n = 6/7$) 608.96 ± 425.59 ng/m³ (CV 69.9 %), Mělník ($n = 14/15$) 134.00 ± 49.35 ng/m³ (CV 36.8 %). For the full dataset ($n = 26/31$), the mean is 164.99 ± 83.55 ng/m³ (CV 50.6 %). Only 21 compounds are shared at ≥ 60 % and 16 at ≥ 75 %. Although this shared core is relatively small, it is expected under stringent thresholds across three regions with different numbers of sites. The shared set is chemically consistent with lignocellulosic pyrolysis – dominated by anhydrosugars (levoglucosan/levoglucosenone), furans/furanones and phenols – forming a robust biomass core. Compared with the “Coal dataset”, whose shared core contains more non-specific combustion products (notably ubiquitous aliphatics and other components), the “Biomass core” is clearly enriched in lignocellulosic pyrolysis markers, providing a more source-specific signal across regions.

Emissions from coal combustion contain monocarboxylic acids ($<C_9$), up to 31–65 % of aromatic hydrocarbons (toluene, xylene, ethylbenzene, benzene, trimethylbenzene, and styrene) but also phenolic compounds, such as phenol, o-cresol, and p-cresol, which have the highest variability in emissions influenced by the properties of coal and the conditions of the combustion process (Cheng et al., 2018). The concentrations of compounds ($\Sigma 129$) originating from coal combustion in PM₁₀ ranged from 14 to 1874 ng/m³.

A total of 130 compounds associated with coal combustion were identified. After removing anomalous values using the $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ rule, arithmetic means and sample standard deviations (SD) were computed for each region: Zdíby ($n = 8/9$) 115.85 ± 47.32 ng/m³ (CV 41 %), Ústí ($n = 7/7$) 736.34 ± 635.03 ng/m³ (CV 86 %), and Mělník ($n = 13/15$) 42.68 ± 19.57 ng/m³ (CV 46 %). The mean for the whole dataset ($n = 26/31$) is 94.37 ± 78.61 ng/m³ (CV 83 %). The high CV in Ústí indicates episodic/heterogeneous sources and variable dispersion; Mělník exhibits the lowest levels with relatively limited variability; Zdíby falls in between. Based on occurrence thresholds of ≥ 60 % and ≥ 75 % of locations, the regional profiles partially overlap but differ in breadth. At ≥ 60 %

($\geq 75\%$), the number of above-threshold compounds is 68 (65) in Ústí, 58 (56) in Zdíby, and 52 (47) in Mělník. A robust shared core is present: 15 compounds occur in all three regions at $\geq 60\%$ and 14 compounds at $\geq 75\%$. Across all locations, 29 compounds meet the $\geq 60\%$ threshold and 25 meet $\geq 75\%$, indicating that part of the spectrum is regionally widespread while the remainder is more local in character.

Chemical group composition varies by region yet retains a shared component. At the $\geq 60\%$ threshold, Zdíby and Ústí are dominated by polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs; Z: 19, U: 19) together with aliphatic hydrocarbons (Z: 13, U: 14); N-heteroaromatics are also notable in Zdíby (10). Mělník contrasts with a higher share of oxygenated aliphatics (17), followed by aliphatic hydrocarbons (10) and PAHs (7). The values at $\geq 75\%$ are similar (PAHs + aliphatics in Ústí/Zdíby; oxygenated aliphatics in Mělník). The shared core across regions consists mainly of aliphatic hydrocarbons (6) and oxygenated aliphatics (5), with a smaller PAH contribution (3 at 60%; 2 at 75%). This pattern is consistent with a coal-combustion signal (PAHs) while highlighting the role of secondary/oxygenated components and ubiquitous aliphatics in the regional background.

Pollution from transport is characterised by a combination of semi-volatile organic compounds (SVOCs) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs), representing a diverse spectrum of chemical species. SVOCs include compounds with relatively high molecular weights, such as alkanes, carboxylic acids, aldehydes and ketones, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and geochemical markers. VOCs are primarily represented by aromatic hydrocarbons, such as alkylated benzenes, including 1,2,3-trimethylbenzene, 1-ethynyl-4-methylbenzene, 1-methoxy-4-methylbenzene, 1-methyl-3-(1-methylethenyl)benzene, and 1-methyl-3-(1-methylethyl)benzene.

A total of 117 transport-derived compounds were evaluated. By occurrence thresholds, the profiles diverge at $\geq 60\%$ ($\geq 75\%$), Zdíby has 48 (48) compounds, Ústí 59 (59), and Mělník 60 (50). The three-region overlap is 26 (23) compounds; across all sites, it is 55 (39). Transport-derived compounds were found in the range of 33–1847 ng/m³. After removing anomalies with the 1.5 \times IQR rule, summed “traffic” compounds are: Zdíby ($n = 9/9$) 290.40 \pm 146.88 ng/m³ (CV 50.6%), Ústí ($n = 7/7$) 1683.67 \pm 1188.03 ng/m³ (CV 70.6%), and Mělník ($n = 57/57$) 164.37 \pm 63.30 ng/m³ (CV 38.5%). The mean for the whole dataset ($n = 65/73$) is 175.06 \pm 72.85 ng/m³ (CV 41.6%). Ústí shows the highest levels and variability; Mělník combines lower means with the smallest variability; Zdíby are intermediate.

Across all three regions, compounds associated with traffic and biomass combustion prevail over those from coal combustion. In Ústí, traffic-related compounds dominate, alongside a substantial contribution from coal and biomass. The high variability in both occurrence and concentrations indicates episodic sources (traffic peaks, cold starts, road hubs) and the influence of variable local heating, i.e., a mixture of line and point sources with short-term spikes. Zdíby shows an intermediate burden with a predominance of traffic and biomass; variability is moderate and consistent with a mixed regime (nearby roads and dispersed domestic heating) without pronounced extremes. In Mělník, traffic and biomass contributions are comparable and variability in occurrence and concentrations is the lowest, indicating a more spatially uniform and stable background; the coal signal is weak. Similar dominant sources traffic emissions, biomass burning, and industrial activity, were also identified by [Pongpiachan et al. \(2025b\)](#).

3.2. Compounds of biogenic origin

Terrestrial ecosystems emit large amounts of biogenic volatile organic compounds (BVOCs), the main components of which are isoprene (~70%), monoterpenes (~11%) and sesquiterpenes (~2.5%). These highly reactive substances form oxidation products that can initiate the formation of new particles or promote the growth of existing particles, thus contributing to the formation of secondary organic aerosols (SOAs) ([Song et al., 2024a](#)). Biogenic compounds in PM₁₀ can comprise 5–50% ([Waked et al., 2014](#)). The biogenic component in PM₁₀ corresponds to 10–25%, which is probably related to sampling in the winter period, when the production of biogenic VOCs is lowest ([Dörter et al., 2020](#)).

In biogenic matter in PM₁₀, compounds from the isoprene and terpene groups, aldehydes, ketones (heptanone, hexenone, decanone, etc.), alkanols, and some fatty carboxylic acids are included. A total of 99 compounds were identified. During the monitoring period, the concentrations of organic compounds indicative of biogenic matter in PM₁₀ ranged from 8.18 to 694.94 ng/m³. After excluding anomalous values, the highest average concentration of biogenic matter was recorded in Ústí ($n = 7/7$), at 409.94 \pm 189.68 ng/m³ (CV 46.3%), while the lowest was observed in Mělník ($n = 20/21$), at 26.88 \pm 11.12 ng/m³ (CV 41.4%). All three regions share a small but stable common core of biogenic compounds (14 at $\geq 75\%$ of sites; 17 at $\geq 60\%$), consisting mainly of linear alkanes (C₁₀–C₁₂, C₃₀–C₃₅) and several typical biogenic terpenes – that is, a regional biogenic background. Above this core, the regions differ in both the breadth of the spectrum and the levels of summed concentrations: Ústí shows the highest and most consistent occurrence and concentrations (the richest mix of local and regional contributions), Zdíby is intermediate, and Mělník exhibits the lowest levels and the narrowest spectrum (a more homogeneous background). It indicates that most biogenic compounds are spatially shared. However, the intensity and diversity of their occurrence are strongly regionally controlled by the local environment/vegetation, microclimate, and the degree of mixing with other sources.

3.3. Chemicals originating from volatile compound products

Volatile compound products, which are capable of releasing VOCs/SVOCs, are another source of air pollution that needs to be addressed. At the monitored sites in this study, PM₁₀ contained 0.03–0.80 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of chemical compounds released from VCPs. These concentrations are comparable to those reported in the literature for California and other U.S. cities (the states New York, New Jersey, and Connecticut), where concentrations ranged from 0.2 to 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ ([Seltzer et al., 2022](#)).

Current research on VCPs is focused on the gaseous phase in the air, which contains chemical compounds released from products

that are used daily. These chemical product groups include cleaners, personal care products, adhesives, sealants, paints, coatings, pesticides, and printing inks, all partially evaporating on atmospherically relevant time scales (Seltzer et al., 2022). For these specific VCPs, compounds called tracers have been defined. PCPs include D5-siloxane; insecticides, p-dichlorobenzene; adhesives, D4-siloxane; anthropogenic fragrances, monoterpene limonene and camphor; coating and paint, parachlorobenzotrifluoride (Gkatzelis et al., 2021).

In PM₁₀ from the study area, chemicals from VCPs are contained in variable concentrations in the range of 0.59–2.11 % with an average value of 1.11 ± 0.25 % relative to the total concentration of all compounds identified. The occurrence of VCP-derived chemical compounds in PM₁₀ particles is related to their concentrations in the air. As part of this study, chemical compounds released from volatile chemical products (VCPs) were classified into nine functional groups based on the intended use of the source products (Fig. 2). Groups of chemical compounds used for personal care products (PCP), food products, printing inks (PI), cleaners and disinfectants (CLA), pharmaceuticals, coatings and chemical compounds derived from plastics were defined. The pesticide group was extended to include agrochemicals. Airborne VOC/SVOC emissions from volatile chemical products (VCPs), identified in the organic fraction of PM₁₀, were classified into two categories based on the material origin: (i) compounds released from plastics and polymer-based products, and (ii) compounds emitted from non-polymer matrices, including pharmaceuticals, dyes, solvents, foods, personal care products (PCPs), and cleaning agents.

Within the identification of all compounds present in PM₁₀, 157 compounds were classified as volatile chemical products (VCPs), of which 106 can be considered unique to product emissions. Compounds were considered unique if they are not of biogenic origin, do not arise from natural environmental processes, are not typically present in common emissions from other sources (e.g., traffic, combustion, cooking), and are characteristic of personal care product (PCP) formulations. Of the 157 compounds, only 18 were

Fig. 2. Classification of VOC/SVOC emissions from VCPs into polymer-based and non-polymer product groups, based on the material origin of the source products.

detected at $\geq 75\%$ of sites per region, simultaneously across Zdíby, Ústí, and Mělník. Ústí shows the most pronounced presence of plastic-related compounds; it has the largest number of compounds above the occurrence threshold ($\geq 75\%$: 91) and the highest totals per site after $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ filtering ($395.01 \pm 217.97 \text{ ng/m}^3$). Mělník shows a nearly comparable breadth ($\geq 75\%$: 85) but lower and more stable totals ($105.55 \pm 35.16 \text{ ng/m}^3$, lowest CV), indicating a more uniform, area-wide burden without pronounced episodes. Zdíby falls between these two ($\geq 75\%$: 47; $93.38 \pm 45.99 \text{ ng/m}^3$). The set of 18 compounds shared by all three regions is dominated by plastic additives such as phthalates and citrate esters used as plasticisers, phosphate additives and flame retardants, and monomeric and degradation products of polymers; this is consistent with a mixture of sources including indoor and outdoor materials, personal care products, and secondary contributions from the surrounding built environment.

Frequently occurring VCP-derived compounds (detected at $\geq 60\%$ of sampling sites) accounted for roughly one-third of the cumulative VCP mass, while less frequent compounds ($< 60\%$) contributed the majority. This pattern indicates that the VCP burden in PM_{10} is largely governed by locally specific emissions and transformation processes rather than uniformly distributed background sources.

3.3.1. Pesticides and agrochemicals

The “pesticides/agrochemicals” group in our dataset contains no clearly identifiable pesticide active ingredients. Compounds flagged in this category are predominantly co-formulants or synthesis intermediates (e.g., phthalate plasticisers, citrate esters, triacetin, isopropyl myristate, triphenyl phosphate, TCPP), and none meet the $\geq 75\%$ occurrence criterion per region (Zdíby, Ústí, Mělník). Occasional detections of 1,3-isobenzofurandione (phthalic anhydride) and related phthalic-anhydride derivatives at multiple sites are more consistent with plastic/industrial sources or secondary formation than with agricultural use. In Ústí, the observation of 3,4,5,6-tetrahydrophthalic anhydride likewise points to the transformation of anhydrides within mixed urban emissions, rather than a marker of pesticide application.

3.3.2. Personal care products

Personal care products are composed of several groups of organic substances that can be divided into fragrances, antiseptics, additives, fixatives, preservatives, and solvents according to their effect and use (Balci and Sofuoglu, 2023).

3.3.2.1. Group of volatile fragrance-related compounds in PCPs.

Fragrances released to the air undergo volatilisation, photolysis, and reactions with atmospheric oxidants and are removed by dry and wet deposition (Rádis-Baptista, 2023). Reported health effects include cutaneous, respiratory, and systemic outcomes such as headaches, asthma attacks, respiratory problems, and cardiovascular or neurological symptoms (Rádis-Baptista, 2023). Many fragrance formulations incorporate both naturally derived terpenoids (e.g., α -pinene, limonene, myrcene) and synthetically produced aroma compounds, including musk-type substances, which contribute to the overall scent profile and volatility of personal care and household products. Terpenoids used in fragrance formulations also occur naturally in the environment, particularly as biogenic NMVOCs emitted by coniferous vegetation. Their dual presence in both anthropogenic products and natural emissions underscores the need to distinguish between source types when interpreting ambient concentrations. For this study, terpene compounds were classified according to their origin and functional use and subsequently assigned to one of three groups: (i) compounds used in personal care and cleaning agents (PCPs and CLAs), (ii) compounds of biogenic origin, and (iii) compounds associated with biomass burning emissions.

Biogenic NMVOCs from conifers include α -pinene, camphene, sabinene, β -pinene, and myrcene, with smaller emissions of β -phellandrene and α -terpinene (Cho et al., 2017; Kopaczyk et al., 2020; Sorvari and Hartikainen, 2021). Secondary products such as *o*-*p*-cymene and *p*-mentha-1,3,8-triene arise via photochemical or thermal dehydrogenation of α -terpinene and α -phellandrene (Spraul et al., 1991). Limonene biotransformation yields (+)-dihydrocarveol, α -terpineol, and *p*-menthane-1,2-diol (Grabarczyk et al.,

Fig. 3. Concentrations of biogenic terpenes with respect to their natural occurrence and use in cosmetic products (a); terpenes detected in more than 75% of analysed samples, including biogenic compounds such as camphene and 1,3,8-p-menthatriene (b).

2020). α -Thujone is reported for cypress-family species in the Czech Republic, where terpene profiles are highly variable and α - β -pinene and β -phellandrene are also abundant (Malhocká and Šváblová, 2023). In addition to their biogenic origin, α -pinene, β -pinene, limonene, and camphene are major components of emissions during open biomass burning (Li et al., 2024b).

In total, 30 compounds were assigned to the PCP group, of which 21 were terpenoids commonly used as fragrances, flavours, or repellents. These included biogenic terpenes (e.g., (+)-dihydrocarveol, α -terpineol, limonene, camphor), synthetic fragrance fixatives (e.g., ethylene brassylate), and essential oil constituents from exotic species (e.g., p-menthane, p-menthan-3-one, menthogycol, thymol, p-cumenol). Additional compounds such as o-/p-cymene and p-mentha-1,3,8-triene were classified as secondary biogenic products (Fig. 3). Fragrance-related compounds formed the most concentration-dominant subset within the PCP group, highlighting their relevance for source attribution and exposure assessment.

Across all three regions (Fig. 4), terpenes associated with personal care/cleaning products (PCP) exhibit higher concentrations than purely biogenic terpenes. The dataset-level mean concentration of PCP terpenes is 13.07 ± 7.28 ng/m³ (after outlier removal using the $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ rule; $n = 33/37$ sites retained), and for biogenic terpenes, the dataset-level mean is 7.77 ± 5.27 ng/m³ ($1.5 \times \text{IQR}$; $n = 36/37$). Ústí leads both in the number of above-threshold terpenes and in concentration levels (PCP 38.65 ± 23.85 ng/m³ and biogenic 11.20 ± 5.56 ng/m³). Zdíby shows a similar pattern (PCP 14.44 ± 6.54 and biogenic 3.13 ± 1.68 ng/m³), indicating a pronounced influence of local human activities (households, services). In Mělník, the biogenic background is relatively strong, and the PCP advantage is only slight (10.73 ± 5.18 and 8.13 ± 4.13 ng/m³), although the VCP contribution remains relevant. Practically, targeting emissions from personal-care/cleaning products is likely to be most effective in Ústí and Zdíby, whereas in Mělník the biogenic background prevails. At the ≥ 75 % site-presence threshold, the most often detected PCP/VCP-associated compounds were limonene, p-cymene, and α -terpineol. Galaxolide (HHCB) was not detected in Zdíby but occurred at 93 % of sites in Ústí and ~ 55 % in Mělník (overall ~ 43 %). We therefore treat HHCB as a regionally relevant PCP tracer, particularly in Ústí, rather than a universal marker across all regions. The shared PCP signal is better represented by the macrocyclic musk ethylene brassylate.

This estimate primarily serves to demonstrate that potential overlap between biogenic and PCP-type BVOCs is limited (4–11 % of ΣBVOCs), corresponding to < 3 % of total PM_{10} even under a conservative reassignment. Therefore, the overlap does not materially affect the overall source apportionment but highlights that a measurable fraction of atmospheric BVOCs may originate from consumer product use, consistent with literature showing substantial urban contributions from volatile chemical products (e.g., Seltzer et al. (2022)).

This subsection would also include information on plasticisers used in cosmetics; however, to avoid duplication with their description in polymeric materials and other non-polymer matrices, these details are provided exclusively in subsection 3.3.7.

Compounds influencing properties of cosmetic products, such as methyl dihydroabietate, isopropyl myristate, 2,4-dimethyl-1-hexene, phthalamide agent, benzamide, N,N-diethyl-4-methyl-benzamide (DEET), and triphenyl phosphate, show the most significant variability in concentrations and occurrence at individual sites. PM_{10} samples from Ústí exhibited the highest concentrations and variability of additional chemical compounds associated with personal care products (PCPs). After removing outliers ($1.5 \times \text{IQR}$), the mean concentration reached 70.77 ± 66.83 ng/m³, with a coefficient of variation (CV) of 94.4 %. In contrast, Mělník showed the lowest and most stable levels (8.65 ± 1.35 ng/m³; CV 15.7 %), while Zdíby presented intermediate concentrations (17.37 ± 9.22 ng/m³; CV 53.1 %). Compounds commonly detected across all three regions (≥ 75 % of sites) were predominantly co-formulants and solvents, including isopropyl myristate (IPM) and triacetin. Isopropyl palmitate (IPP) was present in all regions only at the ≥ 60 % threshold. The overall mean concentration of additional PCP-related compounds in the dataset was 12.00 ± 7.36 ng/m³ (CV 61.4 %). This distinction between plasticisers and additional PCP-related compounds allows for more precise interpretation of emission sources and functional roles. While plasticisers are primarily associated with formulation stability and texture, the broader PCP-related group reflects a diverse array of cosmetic functionalities, including fragrance delivery, repellents, and solvent behaviour.

No statistically significant correlation was observed between the total concentration of PCP-related compounds and PM_{10} , nor between phthalates and compounds affecting cosmetic properties. A weaker statistical association ($r = 0.61$, $\alpha = 0.1$) was found

Fig. 4. Concentrations of compounds classified as personal care product (PCP) constituents, grouped according to their functional use.

between fragrance/flavour compounds and PM₁₀, which aligns with findings by (Andersson et al., 2022), who reported a correlation between PM_{2.5} and odour-related emissions. Importantly, a statistically significant correlation ($r = 0.67$, $\alpha = 0.05$, $n = 29$) was confirmed between fragrance/flavour compounds and phthalates, supporting the hypothesis that phthalates are used to enhance formulation stability and prolong the olfactory effect of volatile ingredients.

The consistently high PCP share (32–42 %) observed across all sites aligns with previous findings that personal care and consumer products represent one of the dominant sources of volatile chemical products in urban air (Coggon et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2018; Seltzer et al., 2022). These compounds include fragrances, emollients, and plasticisers commonly released through the use of cosmetics, cleaning agents, and other consumer formulations. Their substantial contribution at both industrial (Ústí, 42.4 %) and non-industrial sites (Zdiby and Mělník, 32–42 %) indicates that PCP-related emissions are not confined to local production or industrial activities but reflect widespread consumer behaviour. Similar urban studies have shown that PCPs can rival or exceed traditional combustion-related VOC sources in densely populated environments. Consequently, the strong PCP signal in our dataset likely represents a mixed consumer–industrial origin, emphasising the growing importance of volatile consumer products in PM-bound organic matter.

3.3.3. Printing inks

The “printing inks” (PIs) group included nine compounds, of which only two can be considered as unique: 2-pyrrolidinone and, 1,1'-(1-cyclobutene-1,2-diyl)bis-benzene. None of these compounds is found in PM₁₀ particles at the Zdiby and Mělník sampling sites. 2-pyrrolidinone is associated with printing processes (Wang et al., 2019), while 1,1'-(1-cyclobutene-1,2-diyl)bis-benzene is specifically linked to inks and printing processes used in packaging materials (Vera et al., 2023). Other compounds may also come from PIs: butyl citrate, 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (2-HEMA), DBP, hexanoic acid, 1-ethyl-, methyl stearate, and tributyl phosphate. 2-HEMA is used to increase the hydrophobicity or surface adhesion of polymers and polymer-based materials such as special coatings, resins, adhesives, printing inks, and acrylic plastics. This limited occurrence of unique compounds indicates that the printing inks (PIs) group does not represent a significant source of volatile chemical products (VCPs) within the analysed sample.

3.3.4. Cleaners

Compounds used in cleaning agents (CLA) cannot be reliably defined by a single chemical marker, as they frequently overlap with substances commonly found in personal care products (PCPs). This functional and application-based overlap significantly limits the ability to assign individual compounds to a specific source. Many substances, such as fragrance ingredients, solvents, or co-formulants (e.g., limonene, isopropyl myristate, triacetin, thymol, isopropyl palmitate, benzyl alcohol) are routinely present in both product categories, complicating their interpretation in atmospheric measurements. Thymol (terpene derivative) is a cost-effective, safe, and eco-preferred disinfectant used in cosmetics, food products, and cleaning agents (Strantzali et al., 2021).

In this study, thymol was identified in PM₁₀ across all sampling sites, confirming its widespread occurrence. In contrast, 4,8,12,16-tetramethylheptadecan-4-olide and 4,5-epoxy-trans-carene, compounds also used in both PCP and CLA formulations, were detected exclusively at the Ústí site. This limited occurrence suggests a localised origin and potential link to region-specific emission sources.

3.3.5. Coatings

The following products are included in the “coating” (COAs) group: paints, solvents, thinners, pigments, putty, polishes, and waxes. Compounds such as 4-hydroxy-4-methylpentan-2-one (diacetone alcohol) and methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) are typical solvents used in coating formulations and can be considered unique markers for this application domain. The compound p-aminotoluene serves as a precursor for dye synthesis, while 1,3-butadiene acts as an indirect indicator due to its role in the production of polymeric binders commonly found in paints. Solvents and co-formulants (MIBK, diacetone alcohol, dioxolane) significantly contribute to the chemical profile of PM₁₀, particularly in the Ústí region, where pronounced episodes of elevated concentrations were observed. These episodes likely reflect local activities involving cosmetics, cleaning agents, and coating products, resulting in high spatial variability across sampling sites. Dioxolane is more evenly distributed across Mělník, albeit at low to moderate levels, suggesting a diffuse background of common solvents. p-aminotoluene appears consistently in urban areas and aligns with contributions from hair cosmetics and dye-containing products, indicating links to domestic and service-sector activities. Compounds such as p-terphenyl and (E,E)-1,4-diphenyl-1,3-butadiene behave as aromatic co-occurring species with lower detection frequencies, appearing more episodically.

Based on occurrence frequency, compounds were further classified by their spatial significance. Globally significant compounds include dioxolane, p-aminotoluene, 4-hydroxy-4-methylpentan-2-one, (E,E)-1,4-diphenyl-1,3-butadiene, and MIBK. Locally significant compounds included p-terphenyl and phthalide, which were detected exclusively in Ústí. Silanes are widely used in advanced coating systems as adhesion promoters, crosslinking agents, and surface modifiers, and have also been applied to improve the surface quality of cement-based materials (Cai et al., 2016). Their exclusive detection in the Ústí region suggests localised industrial or construction-related activities involving silane-based formulations.

3.3.6. Pharmaceuticals, food products, and others

The group of compounds that originated from “pharmaceuticals” included seven compounds, of which two are unique. Alpha-myrrin is used as an immunostimulant and anti-inflammatory agent; it was identified only at locations in Ústí. The second compound is N,N-dimethylhexanamide, which was identified only in PM₁₀ in Zdiby.

There are five compounds in the group of “others”, all of which are unique and characteristic of one locality at a time. 1H-Tetrazol-5-amine, a compound used as a propellant or component of explosives (Yang et al., 2017), was identified in Zdiby. A diaper component, 1-methylethyl-cyclohexane, has been identified in the locality of Ústí. Tetrazine compounds, including 1,2,4,5-tetrazine

and its derivative 3,6-dimethyl-s-tetrazine, were identified in Ústí. These compounds are valued for their photophysical and electrochemical properties, which make them suitable for applications in electronic devices, luminescent materials, and photoelectric conversion elements (Lipunova et al., 2021).

Although ten compounds were initially considered food-related, only a subset can be reliably attributed to food sources based on their origin, occurrence, and documented associations. Seven compounds exhibit limited spatial occurrence and may reflect food-associated emissions: 2-phenyl-9H-pyrido[2,3-b]indole, typically formed during the preparation of grilled or pan-fried meat (Nadeem et al., 2021); 4,5-epoxy-trans-carene, a monoterpene with potential culinary relevance; pentyl benzoate, a compound originating from sunflower and proposed as a marker for sunflower oil (Liu et al., 2020); 4-oxohex-2-enal, a lipid oxidation product; triethyl citrate (E1505), used as a food additive and stabiliser; 1,3-diacetin (E1517), which may also occur as a biodiesel component (Sedghi et al., 2022); and dehydromevalonic lactone, a flavour ingredient associated with aged cheese (Palermo et al., 2024). However, due to their multifunctional applications and potential overlap with other product categories (e.g., cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, industrial solvents), these compounds were not included in the final food-specific panel. Notably, 2-phenyl-9H-pyrido[2,3-b]indole was exclusively detected in Mělník, suggesting a locally specific source potentially linked to food processing, thermal degradation, or combustion-related emissions.

Fig. 5. Summary concentrations of chemical compounds in the “plastics” group, categorised by (a) material origin: plasticisers, polymer-related compounds (PP), and non-polymer matrices (NP); and (b) functional use in VCP manufacturing, including monomers, solvents, transport media, reactive modifiers, and crosslinking agents.

3.3.7. Plastic and polymer-related compounds

The “plastics” group includes compounds associated with production processes – such as monomers, additives, polymer condensation precursors, solvent systems, transport media for polymeric formulations, reactive modifiers, and crosslinking agents – as well as compounds released during use, including degradation products (Fig. 5).

The primary sources of plastics in the environment are food and food packaging, containers, bottles, and plastic bags (Maddela et al., 2023). Recently, fibre fragments released from garments and home textiles during washing, drying, and wearing (Periyasamy and Tehrani-Bagha, 2022) are considered a source of environmental pollution and health hazards. Additives are used in the production of plastics that influence the properties of the final products, such as flexibility (plasticisers), heat/flame resistance, longevity, anti-fouling, and surface properties (Hahladakis et al., 2018). Up to 10,000 chemical compounds can be used as additives. Additives are not covalently linked with the parent polymer, which causes their release in the form of particles or extracts (Wiesinger et al., 2021). Colourants and pigments determine the colour of the product; the filling material influences the price and the stability of the components used (Gunaalan et al., 2020). Additives, in particular plasticisers, are used in a wide range of products: electronics, personal care products, food packages, adhesives and inks, toys, and also building materials (Munyaneza et al., 2023).

Out of 34 compounds classified as monomers for polymerisation, precursors for polymer condensation, solvent systems, reactive modifiers, and crosslinking agents, only seven met the $\geq 75\%$ occurrence threshold across all sampling sites. Two compounds, α -methylstyrene and methacrylamide, are directly linked to polymer matrices. Caprolactam was frequently detected and is associated with the degradation of nylon-based materials (nylon 6), including carpets, textiles, and packaging. Additional compounds such as collidine and phthalimide are used in epoxy, polyamide, and acrylate systems, with phthalimide also serving agrochemical functions. Pyrazole and its substituted derivatives act as polymer modifiers, enhancing durability, surface interaction, and photostability. Succinimide functions as a crosslinking agent in polyamide and epoxy formulations. Acrylate and epoxy systems often contain residual monomers (e.g., methyl methacrylate, glycidyl methacrylate) that do not fully cure, leading to the release of low-molecular-weight, highly volatile compounds into the atmosphere.

The detected compounds represent primary constituents of plastic materials released into the atmosphere through mechanical abrasion, fragmentation, or thermal degradation. Their presence is typically associated with local emission sources, such as construction surfaces, packaging residues, or exposed polymeric coatings. Markedly elevated concentrations were observed in Ústí ($12.89 \pm 10.85 \text{ ng/m}^3$; CV=84 %), likely reflecting intensive local degradation of polymeric surfaces and direct industrial emissions. In contrast, lower concentrations in Zdíby ($1.89 \pm 2.13 \text{ ng/m}^3$) and Mělník ($5.53 \pm 2.95 \text{ ng/m}^3$; CV=53 %) may indicate reduced mechanical stress, lower prevalence of polymeric surfaces, or microclimatic conditions less conducive to degradation. Given their limited volatility and low atmospheric transport potential, these compounds are best interpreted as indicators of localised material breakdown rather than long-range pollution vectors. Elevated concentrations of compounds associated with the production of epoxy and alkyd resins (a type of polyester resin) in Ústí are consistent with known industrial activities at Spolchemie (Association for Chemical and Metallurgical Production, joint stock company).

Although monomer concentrations were lowest in Zdíby, the highest average concentration of precursor compounds ($9.02 \pm 5.8 \text{ ng/m}^3$) was observed in this area. This suggests the influence of heterogeneous sources, including various polymeric surfaces, construction materials, and consumer products. The discrepancy between monomer and precursor abundance may reflect the broader functional diversity of precursor compounds, many of which are semi-volatile and released gradually from aged or treated materials rather than active polymerisation processes.

Within the group “Solvent systems and transport media for polymeric formulations,” six compounds were evaluated, of which only N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAc) was detected in more than 60 % of sampling sites, specifically in Zdíby and Mělník. DMAc is widely used as a solvent in the production of polyamides (e.g., nylon), polyurethanes, and epoxy resins. In this case, the highest concentrations were observed in Zdíby ($2.93 \pm 1.45 \text{ ng/m}^3$), suggesting potential influence from heterogeneous sources such as polymeric surfaces, construction materials, or consumer products. The elevated presence of DMAc may reflect secondary emissions from treated materials or local industrial activities involving polymer processing.

Ústí exhibited significantly elevated mean concentrations and variability ($31.38 \pm 29.87 \text{ ng/m}^3$; CV=95 %), suggesting intensive local use or production of polymeric crosslinking agents. These may originate from industrial applications, surface coatings, or modified plastic materials. The high concentration is primarily attributed to succinimide, a known crosslinking agent in polyamide and epoxy systems. Among other compounds relevant to this group, 2-ethyl-3,5-dimethylpyridine was detected consistently across all sites in Zdíby and Mělník, yet its occurrence remains spatially limited. It is used as a functional additive in epoxy, polyamide, and acrylate matrices, from which it can be readily released. Given its role in the formulation of epoxy and alkyd resins – products manufactured at Spolchemie (Ústí) – this compound may be considered an indirect polymer additive marker for the Ústí region.

Compounds classified as “polymer degradation by-products” represent secondary products formed during ageing, oxidation, and mechanical fragmentation of polymeric materials. A total of 25 compounds were assigned to this group, of which only two exceeded the 75 % occurrence threshold and can be considered globally relevant. One of them, 7,9-di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9-diene-2,8-dione (Irganox 1010), is a well-known antioxidant used in plastics, particularly polyethylene (PE) and other polyolefins (Kalweit et al., 2023). It serves as a typical marker for polymer stabilisers and enters the atmosphere via gradual migration from plastic products such as packaging, films, and technical components. Due to its low vapour pressure, it is considered semi-volatile and can be detected in the organic fraction of PM₁₀. Degradation products of polystyrene, such as 1,3,5-triphenylcyclohexane and (\pm)-1,2-diphenyl-1,2-ethanediol photodegradation product of benzophenone, were found at locations in Ústí and Mělník (>occurrence 60 %). The second compound, 4-methylphthalic anhydride (4-MPA), is released primarily as a by-product of industrial processes or through degradation of polymeric materials, where it functions as a reactive component (e.g., in PET, PBT, and epoxy systems). With low to moderate volatility, it may occur both in the gas phase and adsorbed onto particles (SVOCs), where it can persist for several days. The occurrence

of polymer degradation by-products in ambient air is typically linked to local emission sources such as construction materials, packaging plastics, or surfaces exposed to UV radiation. Given their reactivity and limited volatility stability, these compounds exhibit low potential for long-range transport, which is reflected in their spatially restricted distribution.

Markedly higher concentrations of polymer degradation products observed in Ústí ($46.18 \pm 25.35 \text{ ng/m}^3$) likely reflect intensive local degradation of polymer surfaces and direct industrial emissions. In contrast, lower concentrations in Zdíby ($6.62 \pm 4.58 \text{ ng/m}^3$) and Mělník ($7.83 \pm 3.25 \text{ ng/m}^3$) suggest either reduced exposure to polymeric materials or differing microclimatic conditions affecting degradation rates.

3.3.7.1. The group of additives. Most chemical compounds used as additives in plastics serve to modify flexibility and mechanical properties. However, three compounds – benzophenone, triphenyl phosphate (TPHP), and tris(1-chloro-2-propyl) phosphate (TCPP) fulfil distinct functional roles beyond plasticisation. Benzophenone acts primarily as a UV stabiliser, protecting polymer matrices from photodegradation. They are classified as emerging contaminants because of their toxicities (Wang et al., 2023).

Benzophenones are used as UV filters in sunscreens, cosmetics, and personal care products, but also in other products such as food packaging and additives in textiles, plastics, and paints (Gavrila et al., 2023). TPHP functions as both a flame retardant and a plasticiser, contributing to fire resistance in polymeric systems. TCPP is widely used as a flame retardant and functional additive in polyurethane foams, coatings, and plastic formulations. These compounds exemplify non-plasticising additives that enhance the durability, safety, and environmental stability of polymeric materials. Triphenyl phosphate (TPHP) and tris(1-chloro-2-propyl) phosphate (TCPP) belong to the class of organophosphate esters (OPEs), which are widely used in household products and industrial formulations to inhibit flame propagation. These compounds pose significant risks to both human health and ecological systems (Liagkouridis et al., 2015). TPHP has been frequently detected in ambient particulate matter, with reported concentrations of 0.17 ng/m^3 in Brazil, 0.20 ng/m^3 in the United States, and 0.11 ng/m^3 in Poland and China (Gonçalves et al., 2023). Its occurrence in PM_{10} is influenced by meteorological parameters such as relative humidity, atmospheric pressure, and wind speed, which affect both its phase distribution and transport dynamics (Gonçalves et al., 2023).

Triphenyl phosphate (TPHP/TPP) was among the most abundant organophosphate esters (OPFRs) detected, reaching 2.12 ng/m^3 in Ústí and accounting for approximately 2.8 % of the total $\Sigma(\text{PAEs}+\text{NPPs})$. Triphenyl phosphate is commonly detected in indoor air, primarily bound to particulate matter, with concentrations typically ranging from 0.1 to 10 ng/m^3 depending on room characteristics, ventilation rates, and the presence of flame-retardant-containing materials (Vardoulakis et al., 2020). In our dataset, triphenyl phosphate also exhibited bridging behaviour between plasticiser-rich/consumer and coatings/industrial signals, correlating with ΣNPPs ($r = 0.68$, $p < 0.001$), ΣPAEs ($r = 0.59$, $p = 0.001$), and key markers DEHT/DOTP ($r = 0.62$, $p = 0.011$) and ATBC ($r = 0.54$, $p = 0.002$). This pattern supports a localised enhancement at Ústí consistent with coatings/adhesives activities and nearby industrial influences, while remaining inferential in the absence of substance-specific emissions records.

3.3.7.2. Phthalate plasticisers. Plasticisers form a significant subgroup of organic compounds detected in PM_{10} , originating from both personal care products (PCPs) and plastics or polymers. They include phthalate esters (PAEs) and non-phthalate alternatives (NPPs), which improve flexibility, spreadability, and film-forming properties in a wide range of products.

Historically, phthalates in PCPs have been used as solvents, plasticisers, and film-formers. Diethyl phthalate (DEP) functions as a fragrance stabiliser (Rosen et al., 2024), dibutyl phthalate (DBP) increases the flexibility and chip resistance of nail polishes, and dimethyl phthalate (DMP) is used in hair sprays to reduce film stiffness. Their use is now regulatorily constrained: DBP is banned in EU cosmetics (Annex II, Reg. (EC) No. 1223/2009), DMP is under heightened scrutiny for potential endocrine activity (Lyche, 2017), and DEP – while permitted under general provisions and not restricted by IFRA – is closely monitored. The key implication for interpreting ambient data is that, because of these restrictions, most atmospheric PAEs in PM_{10} are expected to originate from plastics and polymers, while the PCP contribution is minor and largely limited to DEP and DMP in fragrances and aerosols.

In PM_{10} samples, PCP-typical PAEs (DEP, DBP, DMP) were detected at 15 sites at $1.08\text{--}1.80 \text{ ng/m}^3$. Other phthalates, including methyl nonyl phthalate, methyl octadecyl phthalate, phthalic acid, and di(oct-3-yl) phthalate, were also present. The sum of plasticisers attributed to PCPs (PAEs + NPPs) reached $5.50 \pm 2.9 \text{ ng/m}^3$, i.e., $18.7 \pm 8.3 \%$ of all PCP-related compounds in PM_{10} . Spatially, Ústí showed the highest mean ($3.61 \pm 2.52 \text{ ng/m}^3$), where the non-phthalate plasticiser acetyl tributyl citrate (ATBC) dominated, suggesting a strong local source related to cosmetic or plastic additive use. Zdíby was characterised by 2-ethylhexyl and isohexyl benzoates, likely linked to fragrance emissions, while Mělník exhibited the highest diversity of plasticisers, including methyl 3-furoate, methyl nonyl, and methyl octadecyl phthalate.

Beyond PCPs, PAEs are widely used in the plastics and polymer industry to improve flexibility and processability and are associated with endocrine, carcinogenic, and developmental effects (Qadeer et al., 2022). The US EPA and EU list six PAEs as priority pollutants (DMP, DEP, DBP, BBP, DEHP, DNOP), with DEHP and BBP classified as probable/possible human carcinogens (U.S. EPA, 2007). In the atmosphere, PAEs occur in both gas and particle phases: low-molecular-weight PAEs (DEP, DBP, DiBP) are typical of consumer or indoor sources, whereas high-molecular-weight PAEs (DEHP, DiNP, BBP) dominate in PVC and other polymers (Huang et al., 2021). Their behaviour is strongly influenced by temperature and radiation (Huo et al., 2023): at higher temperatures, volatilisation increases, but so does photochemical degradation, resulting in lower concentrations in summer (Munyanzeza et al., 2023). Concentrations are therefore driven more by local emissions than by long-range transport (Guerranti et al., 2019).

After excluding outliers, ΣPAE concentrations were $54.32 \pm 26.11 \text{ ng/m}^3$ in Ústí (CV 48.1 %), $31.08 \pm 21.37 \text{ ng/m}^3$ in Zdíby (CV 68.7 %), and $18.64 \pm 9.53 \text{ ng/m}^3$ in Mělník (CV 51.1 %); overall $28.01 \pm 17.84 \text{ ng/m}^3$ (CV 63.7 %). The priority trio DEP + DBP + DEHP accounted for $41.4 \pm 18.5 \%$ of ΣPAE (lowest share in Zdíby, $33.3 \pm 11.4 \%$). Considering restrictions on cosmetic uses, these

levels support the conclusion that the dominant share of PAEs in PM₁₀ originates from plastics and polymers rather than PCPs.

To reduce risks associated with PAEs, non-phthalate plasticisers (NPPs), also termed alternative plasticisers (APs), are increasingly employed, including adipates, terephthalates, trimellitates, citrates, sebacates, and phosphates (Christia et al., 2019). Typical representatives include DIBA, ATEC, DBS, ATBC, and DEHA, although several show organ and endocrine/reproductive effects in animals (Shinohara et al., 2024). Atmospheric data remain limited; G. Song et al. reported 0.94–54.7 ng/m³ of NPPs in PM_{2.5} across 13 Chinese cities and a link with economic activity. In this study, 13 NPPs were identified; ATBC and TBP occurred at > 75 % of sites, while ATEC, triethyl citrate (TEC), and dimethyl trimellitate (DMTM) appeared at > 60 %. ATBC (a common PVC plasticiser) was present at all locations, confirming its global spread. After excluding outliers, Σ NPP concentrations were highest in Ústí (13.54 ± 1.02 ng/m³; CV 7.5 %), more variable in Zdíby (6.36 ± 5.11 ng/m³; CV 80.3 %), and intermediate in Mělník (7.58 ± 2.41 ng/m³; CV 31.8 %); overall 8.17 ± 3.89 ng/m³ (CV 47.6 %).

A key methodological point is that NPPs are used simultaneously in PCPs and in plastics, coatings, and adhesives; consequently, their source in PM₁₀ cannot be reliably distinguished. We therefore evaluate Σ NPP collectively without source attribution. The Σ NPP/ Σ PAE ratio (Ústí 2.59, Mělník 1.09, Zdíby 0.29) is interpreted as an indicator of the extent of phthalate substitution, not as direct evidence of specific sources. This pattern aligns with Nagorka et al. (2022), who report increasing prevalence of ATBC and DEHT in indoor environments and consumer goods.

The distribution and variability of phthalate esters (PAEs) and non-phthalate plasticisers (NPPs) detected in PM₁₀ across the three sampling regions are summarised in (Fig. 6). The stacked bars illustrate that the chemical composition of NPPs differed substantially among sites: Ústí was dominated by citrates and adipates, whereas Zdíby contained higher proportions of trimellitates and organophosphates. Mělník showed a more balanced mixture of all groups. The boxplots demonstrate that Σ NPP concentrations were consistently higher than Σ PAE values in Ústí and comparable in Mělník, while Zdíby exhibited the lowest and most variable levels. The

Fig. 6. Concentrations and relative proportions of phthalate and non-phthalate plasticisers (NPPs) in PM₁₀ across the three study regions. (a) Distribution of NPP groups by chemical class; (b) Boxplot of summed NPP and PAE concentrations at individual sites; (c) Ratios of Σ NPP/ Σ PAE as an indicator of the degree of phthalate substitution. The data highlight spatial differences, with Ústí showing the highest NPP concentrations and substitution ratios, indicating a predominance of modern, non-phthalate plasticisers, while Zdíby exhibits a legacy PAE profile.

$\Sigma\text{NPP}/\Sigma\text{PAE}$ ratios emphasise these spatial differences: the highest ratio in Ústí (2.6) indicates a strong predominance of non-phthalate compounds and suggests ongoing substitution of legacy PAEs; Mělník (1.1) reflects a transitional profile, whereas Zdíby (0.3) remains influenced mainly by older, phthalate-rich emissions. Overall, the graphical trends support the conclusion that industrial and consumer product emissions in Ústí are characterised by a more advanced shift toward non-phthalate formulations, consistent with the regional concentration data and substitution patterns discussed above.

No significant correlation was found between total PCP-related compounds and PM_{10} mass; the fragrance/flavour vs. PM_{10} relationship was weaker ($r = 0.61, \alpha = 0.1$), consistent with (Andersson et al., 2022) for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and odour emissions. By contrast, fragrance/flavour compounds and PAEs were significantly correlated ($r = 0.67, \alpha = 0.05, n = 29$), supporting the hypothesis that phthalates stabilise fragrances and prolong their perception in formulations.

The results demonstrate that both phthalate and non-phthalate plasticisers are ubiquitous in airborne PM_{10} , with apparent spatial

Fig. 7. Source-specific share of organic matter within PM_{10} (a); PCA biplot of compound group contributions for source profile interpretation (b).

variability among the three study regions. Σ PAE concentrations (18–54 ng/m³) fall within the lower range of values reported for urban areas in China and are comparable to or slightly below those observed in southern Europe (Guerranti et al., 2019; Huang et al., 2022; Song et al., 2024b). Σ NPP levels (6–14 ng/m³) are an order of magnitude lower than in highly industrialised Asian regions but exceed those reported for background and rural European sites, confirming that substitution processes are underway in Central Europe. The elevated Σ NPP/ Σ PAE ratio in Ústí indicates an advanced transition towards non-phthalate compounds, while Zdiby still reflects a legacy phthalate signature. Overall, the findings suggest that regional emissions mirror the broader global trend of declining phthalate use and progressive replacement with alternative plasticisers, though total concentrations remain environmentally relevant and warrant continued monitoring.

3.4. Assessment of compounds released from VCPs as a source of pollution

Across the three monitored locations, Zdiby, Ústí, and Mělník distinct patterns emerged in the distribution of compound groups associated with polymeric materials, consumer products, and industrial applications (Fig. 7). Ústí exhibited elevated concentrations of polymer degradation by-products (9.31 ng/m³), crosslinking agents and modifiers (6.33 ng/m³), and multifunctional compounds (17.39 ng/m³), reflecting its industrial character and known activities linked to epoxy and alkyd resin production. Plasticisers for personal care products (PCPs) were also most abundant in Ústí (14.69 ng/m³), suggesting handling or processing cosmetic and pharmaceutical packaging materials.

Zdiby presented a more diversified profile, with the highest levels of precursors (6.09 %), non-phthalate solvents (3.48 %), and plasticisers for polymers (15.16 %), indicative of heterogeneous sources such as consumer products, construction materials, and treated surfaces. It also recorded the highest concentrations of compounds classified as fragrances, flavourings, food additives, and pharmaceuticals (21.61 %), pointing to communal emissions and domestic usage patterns.

Mělník stood out for its elevated concentrations of monomers (4.69 %) and plasticisers used in coatings, paints, and inks (7.18 %), suggesting emissions from packaging and surface treatments. Multifunctional compounds were also prominent, indicating a blend of urban and construction-related applications.

These spatial differences are further supported by principal component analysis (PCA, Fig. 7), which reveals structural contrasts among the regions. PC1 captures the gradient between consumer-oriented groups (e.g., fragrances, pharmaceuticals) and industrial groups (e.g., plasticisers, rubber-related compounds), while PC2 separates multifunctional and degradation-related compounds – particularly prominent in Mělník from other categories. The resulting biplot illustrates how specific compound groups contribute to regional variability and highlights the structural emission profile of each locality.

3.4.1. Regionally unique compounds

A total of 180 chemical compounds were evaluated across three study regions. A total of 105 compounds met the criteria and were

Table 1
Regionally unique compounds.

Area	Chemical compound	Origin/utilisation	
Ústí	Methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK)	Solvent	
	(<i>E,E</i>)-1,4-diphenyl-1,3-butadiene	Photoproduct of polymer degradation; regionally elevated in Ústí.	
	1(3 H)-isobenzofuranone (phthalide)	Additive for plastics, coatings, stabilisers, photolithographic and optical applications	
	p-Aminotoluene	Luminophore; dye/pigment and optical material production; surface treatments (possible sources VINYL-FLEX Ltd.)	
Ústí	Dioxolane and 4-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-pentanone (diacetone alcohol)	Solvent and co-formulant compounds; markedly elevated levels in Ústí	
	p-Cymene, Thymol, α -Terpineol (terpenes)	Strong PCP/VCP signal beyond typical biogenic contributions. Thymol - antimicrobial terpenoid.	
Zdiby	Isobutyl benzoate, 2-methylpentyl benzoate, Pentyl benzoate, Heptyl benzoate, 4-hydroxy- $\alpha,\alpha,4$ -trimethylcyclohexanemethanol, 1,3,3-trimethyl-2-oxabicyclo[2.2.2]octan-6-ol, 2,2-dimethyl-3-methylbicyclo[2.2.1]heptane, Triacetin, isopropyl palmitate N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAc)	PCP (fragrance/fixative)	
	Dodecan-1-ol (lauryl alcohol)	Solvent for resins/coatings, polymer/fibre processing	
	2-ethylhexan-1-ol (2-EH)	PCP/cleaning	
	4-methylphthalic anhydride	Off-gassing from PVC/coatings	
	1,2-ethanediol, monobenzoate	Resin/curing intermediate	
	Caprolactam	Plasticiser/solvent for coating	
	Mělník	1H-pyrrole and derivatives	Textile off-gassing
		Acetyl triethyl citrate (ATEC)	Resin/curing intermediate
		Bicyclo[3.1.0]hexan-3-one	PCP & materials (plasticiser/co-formulant)
		Carvone	Fragrance PCP
1H-pyrazole and derivatives		PCP (fragrance)/biogenic	
Isopropyl myristate (IPM)		Industrial/agrochemical intermediate	
Aniline		PCP (emollient/co-formulant)	
Phthalimide	Dye/polyurethane/rubber intermediate; typical industrial marker		
		Imide fungicides, plasticiser chemistry	

classified as regionally unique.

Ústí exhibited the highest number of regionally unique compounds ($n = 51$), reflecting a complex emission profile shaped by industrial activity (e.g., solvents and aromatic markers linked to resin, coating, adhesive, and polymer processing), frequent use of volatile chemical products (VCPs) such as fragrances and cleaners, and episodic concentration peaks (Table 1). This pattern indicates a strong influence from both industrial operations and urban service-related sources, including indoor-to-outdoor transfer. The elevated VCP-to-PM₁₀ ratio (12.10 %) and high concentrations of combustion-related compounds (811.2 ng/m³) and traffic emissions (366.63 ng/m³) further support the presence of reactive precursors contributing to secondary VOC formation (oxidation products: 91.8 ng/m³).

In Mělník, 40 regionally unique compounds were identified. The profile is dominated by fragrance and flavour substances alongside multifunctional co-formulants (e.g., solvents, diluents), with sporadic contributions from crosslinking agents and formulation modifiers. Specific compounds include VCP-related co-formulants such as isopropyl myristate and acetyltriethyl citrate, process-related intermediates like aniline and pyrazole/pyrrole, and a minor terpenoid/fragrance signature represented by carvone and bicyclic ketones. The spatial distribution is uniform, with low variability and minimal industrial influence, indicating a stable residential background. The low VCP-to-PM₁₀ ratio (1.79 %) and reduced levels of combustion and traffic-related compounds suggest limited precursor input for secondary VOC formation.

Zdiby exhibited the lowest number of regionally unique compounds ($n = 14$), primarily consisting of fragrance/flavour terpenoids and material-related classes associated with plastics and textiles (e.g., plasticisers, rubbers, dyes, textile additives). Notable compounds such as N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAC) and caprolactam were attributed to off-gassing from carpets and textiles, reflecting residual emissions from polymer and fibre production. Their presence supports indoor-to-outdoor VOC transfer mechanisms, as documented in

Fig. 8. Origin of PM₁₀ for individual sites (a); average value – the percentage of source apportionment in PM₁₀ (b).

studies on carpet-related emissions and secondary release pathways (Noorian Najafabadi et al., 2022). The profile reflects routine VCP use and slow off-gassing from consumer materials, with industrial solvents playing a minor role. Concentration variability is moderate, without pronounced episodic peaks, and the VCP-to-PM₁₀ ratio (2.28 %) suggests a low contribution of product-derived volatile emissions relative to particulate load.

Overall, the occurrence of regionally unique compounds is shaped more by source type and product use than by atmospheric persistence. The phase association trend remains consistent: VCPs defined by their origin in volatile chemical products are more prevalent across locations than SVOCs/LVOCs, not due to phase behaviour alone but because of widespread consumer and industrial applications. The weak correlation between compound occurrence and persistence ($r \approx 0.15$) further supports that emission profile and product volatility are more decisive than atmospheric lifetime in determining compound presence.

3.5. Origin of particulate matter in PM₁₀ in relation to sources of pollution

With the drastic decline in the operation of large coal-burning energy sources, the amounts of chemical compounds emitted from the combustion of biomass have changed, making it the most important source of PM₁₀, especially in the areas of Mělník and Zdiby, where combustion in local furnaces will contribute to the change of fuels (Fig. 8). A significant source of VOC/SVOC chemical compounds is formed by volatile chemical products, which account for up to 12 % of all identified compounds. Since, in most cases, these are compounds with an effect on human health, it is necessary to pay particular attention to this group, given that we are also exposed to the same compounds in the indoor environment. VCPs, defined as volatile compounds released from consumer and industrial products, predominantly occur in the gas phase and exhibit broader spatial distribution across locations compared to SVOCs/LVOCs, which tend to remain more spatially confined due to their lower volatility and stronger particle-phase affinity.

Across all regions, the concentration of combustion-related compounds and primary VOCs (e.g., traffic, cooking, VCPs) shows a clear association with the abundance of oxidised VOCs, confirming that primary emissions act as precursors for secondary atmospheric transformation. Ústí, with the highest levels of chemical compounds from combustion (811.20 ng/m³), traffic-related VOCs (366.63 ng/m³), and cooking emissions (85.21 ng/m³), also exhibits the highest concentration of oxidised VOCs (91.79 ng/m³), indicating elevated photochemical reactivity and transformation pressure (Fig. 8).

Importantly, Ústí records the highest total VOC load captured in PM₁₀ (2677 ng/m³), despite having a lower overall PM₁₀ mass (22.12 µg/m³) compared to Zdiby (24.82 µg/m³). This disproportion suggests that PM₁₀ particles in Ústí carry a significantly higher share of organic compounds with volatile character, likely due to sorption of gas-phase VOCs, secondary condensation, or direct release from product use with particle-phase affinity.

VCPs (Volatile Chemical Products) refer to compounds released from consumer and industrial products such as cleaners, cosmetics, coatings, and adhesives. While they are typically highly volatile, in this study, they were captured within the PM₁₀ fraction, indicating either sorption onto particles or presence in condensed form. The VCP-to-PM₁₀ ratio in Ústí (12.10 %) underscores the substantial contribution of product-derived organics to the chemical makeup of airborne particles, influencing both direct exposure and secondary chemistry.

In contrast, Mělník and Zdiby show lower VCP/PM₁₀ ratios (1.79 % and 2.28 %, respectively) and reduced concentrations across all categories, reflecting material-driven and indoor-sourced profiles with slower off-gassing and limited precursor input. Their lower levels of oxidised VOCs (21–25 ng/m³) are consistent with reduced atmospheric reactivity and minimal transformation pressure within the particle phase.

Overall, Ústí stands out as the most chemically burdened site, with elevated contributions from combustion, traffic, cooking, and volatile product use, each reinforcing the region's complex and reactive emission profile.

4. Conclusion

This study provides one of the first detailed characterisations of volatile chemical product (VCP) emissions in ambient PM₁₀ in Central Europe. It demonstrates that VCP-related organics, though representing only about 1 % of all identified PM₁₀ constituents, form a distinct and chemically diverse source class with clear spatial signatures. Among conventional sources, traffic and biomass combustion dominated, while coal was regionally limited. The highest overall organic burden occurred in Ústí nad Labem, confirming the impact of mixed industrial and consumer-product influences.

Plasticisers, particularly phthalate esters (PAEs) and non-phthalate plasticisers (NPPs), were pervasive. Given strict EU restrictions on cosmetic PAEs, their presence in PM₁₀ predominantly reflects plastic and polymer emissions rather than personal care products. ΣPAE concentrations (18–54 ng m⁻³) lie within the lower urban range reported globally, while NPPs (6–14 ng m⁻³) show evidence of active substitution. The ΣNPP/ΣPAE ratio (2.6 in Ústí, 1.1 in Mělník, 0.3 in Zdiby) thus serves as a diagnostic indicator of regulatory transition from legacy to alternative plasticisers rather than as a direct source tracer.

The strong correlation between fragrance/flavour compounds and PAEs ($r = 0.67$, $\alpha = 0.05$) suggests that product-derived organics share functional and emission pathways. The predominance of terpenoid and ester-type compounds further highlights the relevance of household and consumer-product chemistry in outdoor air.

In a global context, the observed concentrations are comparable to or lower than those in other urban regions. It confirms that Central Europe is undergoing an early-stage but measurable shift in the chemical composition of PM₁₀. These findings underscore the emerging role of VCPs as a diffuse and under-regulated source of airborne organics, bridging indoor and outdoor environments. Continued monitoring should focus on temporal variability, semi-volatile partitioning, and secondary organic aerosol formation to better quantify their contribution to exposure and air quality management.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Helena Raclavská: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Christoph Pfeifer:** Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Jana Růžicková:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation. **Dagmar Juchelková:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Barbora Švédová:** Visualization, Software, Data curation. **Jitka Hrbek:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Karolina Slamová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Marek Kucbel:** Software, Formal analysis.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.eti.2025.104695](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2025.104695).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Ahn, J., Rao, G., Vejerano, E.P., 2021. Dependence on humidity and aerosol composition of the gas-particle partitioning of weakly and moderately polar VOCs. *Aerosol Air Qual. Res.* 21, 210094. <https://doi.org/10.4209/aaqr.210094>.
- Almeida, S.M., Faria, T., Martins, V., Canha, N., Diapouli, E., Eleftheriadis, K., Manousakas, M.I., 2022. Source apportionment of children daily exposure to particulate matter. *Sci. Total Environ.* 835, 155349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.155349>.
- Amin, M., Prajati, G., Humairoh, G.P., Putri, R.M., Phairuang, W., Hata, M., Furuuchi, M., 2023. Characterization of size-fractionated carbonaceous particles in the small to nano-size range in Batam city, Indonesia. *Heliyon* 9, e15936. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e15936>.
- Andersson, J., Oudin, A., Nordin, S., Forsberg, B., Nordin, M., 2022. PM_{2.5} exposure and olfactory functions. *Int. J. Environ. Health Res.* 32, 2484–2495. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09603123.2021.1973969>.
- Bae, M.-S., Schauer, J.J., Turner, J.R., 2006. Estimation of the monthly average ratios of organic mass to organic carbon for fine particulate matter at an urban site. *Aerosol Sci. Technol.* 40, 1123–1139. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02786820601004085>.
- Balci, E., Sofuoğlu, A., 2023. Fragrance emissions into the air and their impact on air quality and human health. In: Ratola, N., Homem, V. (Eds.), *Fragrances in the Environment, The Handbook of Environmental Chemistry*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 219–264. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-2023-998>.
- Cai, Y., Hou, P., Duan, C., Zhang, R., Zhou, Z., Cheng, X., Shah, S., 2016. The use of tetraethyl orthosilicate silane (TEOS) for surface-treatment of hardened cement-based materials: a comparison study with normal treatment agents. *Constr. Build. Mater.* 117, 144–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2016.05.028>.
- Cheng, J., Zhang, Y., Wang, T., Xu, H., Norris, P., Pan, W.-P., 2018. Emission of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) during coal combustion at different heating rates. *Fuel* 225, 554–562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2018.03.185>.
- Cho, K.S., Lim, Y., Lee, K., Lee, J., Lee, J.H., Lee, L.-S., 2017. Terpenes from forests and human health. *Toxicol. Res.* 33, 97–106. <https://doi.org/10.5487/TR.2017.33.2.097>.
- Christia, C., Poma, G., Harrad, S., De Wit, C.A., Sjöstrom, Y., Leonards, P., Lamoree, M., Covaci, A., 2019. Occurrence of legacy and alternative plasticizers in indoor dust from various EU countries and implications for human exposure via dust ingestion and dermal absorption. *Environ. Res.* 171, 204–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2018.11.034>.
- Coggon, M.M., Gkatzelis, G.I., McDonald, B.C., Gilman, J.B., Schwantes, R.H., Abuhassan, N., Aikin, K.C., Arend, M.F., Berkoff, T.A., Brown, S.S., Campos, T.L., Dickerson, R.R., Gronoff, G., Hurley, J.F., Isaacman-VanWertz, G., Koss, A.R., Li, M., McKeen, S.A., Moshary, F., Peischl, J., Pospisilova, V., Ren, X., Wilson, A., Wu, Y., Trainer, M., Warneke, C., 2021. Volatile chemical product emissions enhance ozone and modulate urban chemistry. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 118, e2026653118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2026653118>.
- Czech Hydrometeorological Institute, 2024. Data collection, processing and evaluation system in 2023.
- Czech Statistical Office, 2024. Characteristics of the Ústí nad Labem Region [WWW Document]. CSU. URL (https://csu.gov.cz/ulk/charakteristika_kraje) (accessed 9.11.24).
- Dörter, M., Odabasi, M., Yenisoý-Karakaş, S., 2020. Source apportionment of biogenic and anthropogenic VOCs in Bolu plateau. *Sci. Total Environ.* 731, 139201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.139201>.
- ECHA, 2025. Information on Chemicals (REACH Registered Substances and Dossiers) [WWW Document]. Eur. Chem. Agency. URL (<https://echa.europa.eu/information-on-chemicals>).
- Ecological Centre Kralupy nad Vltavou, 2022. Evaluation of the air pollution situation in Kralupy nad Vltavou for the year 2022 (in Czech).
- EuPIA, 2023. Guideline on printing inks applied to food contact materials; suitability list of photoinitiators and photosensitizers for low migration UV printing inks. [WWW Document]. Eur. Print. Ink Assoc. URL (<https://www.eupia.org>) (accessed 10.1.25).
- Eurachem, 2025. Eurachem Guide: The fitness for purpose of analytical methods – A laboratory guide to method validation and related topics.
- Flores, R.M., Mertoglu, E., 2020. Optimization of a thermal desorption-gas chromatography/mass spectrometry method for characterization of semi-volatile organic compounds in high time resolved PM_{2.5}. *Atmos. Pollut. Res.* 11, 619–629. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apr.2019.12.016>.
- FSVO, 2023. Ordinance on materials and articles in contact with food (817.023.21) – Annex 10: Printing inks [WWW Document]. Swiss Fed. Food Saf. Vet. Off. URL (<https://www.blv.admin.ch>).

- Gavrila, A.A., Dasteridis, I.S., Tzimas, A.A., Chatzimitakos, T.G., Stalikas, C.D., 2023. Benzophenones in the environment: occurrence, fate and sample preparation in the analysis. *Molecules* 28, 1229. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28031229>.
- Gentner, D.R., Isaacman, G., Worton, D.R., Chan, A.W.H., Dallmann, T.R., Davis, L., Liu, S., Day, D.A., Russell, L.M., Wilson, K.R., Weber, R., Guha, A., Harley, R.A., Goldstein, A.H., 2012. Elucidating secondary organic aerosol from diesel and gasoline vehicles through detailed characterization of organic carbon emissions. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 109, 18318–18323. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1212272109>.
- Gkatzelis, G.I., Coggon, M.M., McDonald, B.C., Peischl, J., Gilman, J.B., Aikin, K.C., Robinson, M.A., Canonaco, F., Prevot, A.S.H., Trainer, M., Warneke, C., 2021. Observations confirm that volatile chemical products are a major source of petrochemical emissions in U.S. cities. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 55, 4332–4343. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c05471>.
- Gonçalves, P.B., Cristale, J., Da Silva, A.A., Nogarotto, D.C., Osório, D.M.M., Romualdo, L.L., Pozza, S.A., 2023. Organophosphate esters (OPEs) in atmospheric particulate matter in different Brazilian regions. *Environ. Sci. Atmospheres* 3, 1533–1540. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3EA00079F>.
- Grabarczyk, M., Mączka, W., Żołnierczyk, A.K., Wińska, K., 2020. Transformations of monoterpenes with the p-menthane skeleton in the enzymatic system of bacteria, fungi and insects. *Molecules* 25, 4840. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25204840>.
- Gu, X., Chu, X., Zeng, X.-L., Bao, H.-R., Liu, X.-J., 2017. Effects of PM_{2.5} exposure on the Notch signaling pathway and immune imbalance in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Environ. Pollut.* 226, 163–173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2017.03.070>.
- Guerranti, C., Martellini, T., Fortunati, A., Scodellini, R., Cincinelli, A., 2019. Environmental pollution from plasticiser compounds: do we know enough about atmospheric levels and their contribution to human exposure in Europe? *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sci. Health* 8, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coesh.2018.10.004>.
- Gunaalan, K., Fabbri, E., Capolupo, M., 2020. The hidden threat of plastic leachates: a critical review on their impacts on aquatic organisms. *Water Res.* 184, 116170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2020.116170>.
- Hahladakis, J.N., Velis, C.A., Weber, R., Iacovidou, E., Purnell, P., 2018. An overview of chemical additives present in plastics: migration, release, fate and environmental impact during their use, disposal and recycling. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 344, 179–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2017.10.014>.
- Hama, S., Ouchen, I., Wyche, K.P., Cordell, R.L., Monks, P.S., 2022. Carbonaceous aerosols in five European cities: insights into primary emissions and secondary particle formation. *Atmos. Res.* 274, 106180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2022.106180>.
- Hilscherová, K., Dušek, L., Šídllová, T., Jállová, V., Čupr, P., Giesy, J.P., Nehyba, S., Jarkovský, J., Klánová, J., Holoubek, I., 2009. Seasonally and regionally determined indication potential of bioassays in contaminated river sediments. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 29, 522–534. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.83>.
- Huang, L., Zhu, X., Zhou, S., Cheng, Z., Shi, K., Zhang, C., Shao, H., 2021. Phthalic acid esters: natural sources and biological activities. *Toxins* 13, 495. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins13070495>.
- Huang, Y.-Q., Zeng, Y., Wang, T., Chen, S.-J., Guan, Y.-F., Mai, B.-X., 2022. PM_{2.5}-bound phthalates and phthalate substitutes in a megacity of southern China: spatiotemporal variations, source apportionment, and risk assessment. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 29, 37737–37747. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-18784-0>.
- Huo, C.-Y., Li, W.-L., Liu, L.-Y., Sun, Y., Guo, J.-Q., Wang, L., Hung, H., Li, Y.-F., 2023. Seasonal variations of airborne phthalates and novel non-phthalate plasticizers in a test residence in cold regions: effects of temperature, humidity, total suspended particulate matter, and sources. *Sci. Total Environ.* 863, 160852. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.160852>.
- IFRA, 2024. IFRA fragrance ingredient glossary: Terms of use [WWW Document]. Int. Fragr. Assoc. IFRA. URL (<https://ifrafragrance.org/priorities/ingredients/glossary/terms>) (accessed 8.1.24).
- ITRC, 2013. Statistics and Sampling for Environmental Data (SBR-1) [WWW Document]. Interstate Technol. Regul. Council. URL (<https://sbr-1.itrcweb.org>) (accessed 10.1.25).
- Kalweit, C., Berger, S., Kämpfe, A., Rapp, T., 2023. Quantification and stability assessment of 7,9-di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9-diene-2,8-dione leaching from cross-linked polyethylene pipes using gas and liquid chromatography. *Water Res.* 243, 120306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2023.120306>.
- Kopaczky, J.M., Warguta, J., Jelonek, T., 2020. The variability of terpenes in conifers under developmental and environmental stimuli. *Environ. Exp. Bot.* 180, 104197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envexpbot.2020.104197>.
- Kulmala, M., Vehkamäki, H., Petäjä, T., Dal Maso, M., Lauri, A., Kerminen, V.-M., Birmili, W., McMurry, P.H., 2004. Formation and growth rates of ultrafine atmospheric particles: a review of observations. *J. Aerosol Sci.* 35, 143–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaerosci.2003.10.003>.
- Kumar, N., 2009. An optimal spatial sampling design for intra-urban population exposure assessment. *Atmos. Environ.* 43, 1153–1155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2008.10.055>.
- Li, Jie, Han, Z., Wu, J., Tao, J., Li, Jiawei, Sun, Y., Liang, L., Liang, M., Wang, Q., 2022. Secondary organic aerosol formation and source contributions over east China in summertime. *Environ. Pollut.* 306, 119383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2022.119383>.
- Li, J., Huang, C., Zhang, C., Wang, H., Song, L., Wang, B., 2024b. Underestimated contribution of open biomass burning to terpenoid emissions revealed by a novel hourly dynamic inventory. *Sci. Total Environ.* 931, 172764. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172764>.
- Li, Xuwei, Ding, D., Xie, W., Li, Xuzhi, Wang, M., Kong, L., Jiang, D., Deng, S., 2023. Spatiotemporal variations and source analysis of VOCs in the environmental air of a typical pesticide remediation site. *Front. Environ. Sci.* 11, 1272836. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2023.1272836>.
- Li, L., Thomsen, D., Wu, C., Priestley, M., Iversen, E.M., Tygesen Skønager, J., Luo, Y., Ehn, M., Roldin, P., Pedersen, H.B., Bilde, M., Glasius, M., Hallquist, M., 2024a. Gas-to-particle partitioning of products from ozonolysis of Δ^3 -carene and the effect of temperature and relative humidity. *J. Phys. Chem. A* 128, 918–928. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.3c07316>.
- Liagkouridis, I., Cousins, A.P., Cousins, I.T., 2015. Physical-chemical properties and evaluative fate modelling of ‘emerging’ and ‘novel’ brominated and organophosphorus flame retardants in the indoor and outdoor environment. *Sci. Total Environ.* 524–525, 416–426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.02.106>.
- Lipunova, G.N., Nosova, E.V., Zyryanov, G.V., Charushin, V.N., Chupakhin, O.N., 2021. 1,2,4,5-Tetrazine derivatives as components and precursors of photo- and electroactive materials. *Org. Chem. Front* 8, 5182–5205. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1Q000465D>.
- Liu, X., Zhang, X., Jin, B., Wang, T., Qian, S., Zou, J., Dinh, V.N.T., Jaffrezou, J.-L., Uzu, G., Dominutti, P., Darfeuille, S., Favez, O., Conil, S., Marchand, N., Castillo, S., De La Rosa, J.D., Grange, S., Hueglin, C., Eleftheriadis, K., Diapouli, E., Manousakas, M.-I., Gini, M., Nava, S., Calzolari, G., Alves, C., Monge, M., Reche, C., Harrison, R.M., Hopke, P.K., Alastuey, A., Querol, X., 2025. Source apportionment of PM₁₀ based on offline chemical speciation data at 24 European sites. *Npj Clim. Atmos. Sci.* 8, 255. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-025-01097-7>.
- Liu, X.-S., Gao, B., Li, X.-L., Li, W.-N., Qiao, Z.-A., Han, L., 2020. Chemical composition and antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of essential oil of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) receptacle. *Molecules* 25, 5244. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25225244>.
- Lyche, J.L., 2017. Phthalates. In: Gupta, G. (Ed.), *Reproductive and Developmental Toxicology*. Elsevier, San Diego, CA, pp. 829–856. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-804239-7.00044-5>.
- Maddala, N.R., Kakarla, D., Venkateswarlu, K., Megharaj, M., 2023. Additives of plastics: entry into the environment and potential risks to human and ecological health. *J. Environ. Manag.* 348, 119364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.119364>.
- Malhocká, A., Švábová, M., 2023. Diversity of the terpene synthesis in the Thuja species – a comparative chemotaxonomic study. *Biochem. Syst. Ecol.* 110, 104703. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bse.2023.104703>.
- Manisalidis, I., Stavropoulou, E., Stavropoulos, A., Bezirtzoglou, E., 2020. Environmental and health impacts of air pollution: a review. *Front. Public Health* 8, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.00014>.
- May, A.A., Nguyen, N.T., Presto, A.A., Gordon, T.D., Lipsky, E.M., Karve, M., Gutierrez, A., Robertson, W.H., Zhang, M., Brandow, C., Chang, O., Chen, S., Cicero-Fernandez, P., Dinkins, L., Fuentes, M., Huang, S.-M., Ling, R., Long, J., Maddox, C., Massetti, J., McCauley, E., Miguel, A., Na, K., Ong, R., Pang, Y., Rieger, P., Sax, T., Truong, T., Vo, T., Chattopadhyay, S., Maldonado, H., Maricq, M.M., Robinson, A.L., 2014. Gas- and particle-phase primary emissions from in-use, on-road gasoline and diesel vehicles. *Atmos. Environ.* 88, 247–260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2014.01.046>.
- McDonald, B.C., De Gouw, J.A., Gilman, J.B., Jathar, S.H., Akherati, A., Cappa, C.D., Jimenez, J.L., Lee-Taylor, J., Hayes, P.L., McKeen, S.A., Cui, Y.Y., Kim, S.-W., Gentner, D.R., Isaacman-VanWertz, G., Goldstein, A.H., Harley, R.A., Frost, G.J., Roberts, J.M., Ryerson, T.B., Trainer, M., 2018. Volatile chemical products emerging as largest petrochemical source of urban organic emissions. *Science* 359, 760–764. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aag0524>.

- Molla, A., Zuo, S., Zhang, W., Qiu, Y., Ren, Y., Han, J., 2022b. Optimal spatial sampling design for monitoring potentially toxic elements pollution on urban green space soil: a spatial simulated annealing and k-means integrated approach. *Sci. Total Environ.* 802, 149728. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.149728>.
- Molla, A., Ren, Y., Zuo, S., Qiu, Y., Li, L., Zhang, Q., Ju, J., Zhu, J., Zhou, Y., 2022a. Evaluating sample sizes and design for monitoring and characterizing the spatial variations of potentially toxic elements in the soil. *Sci. Total Environ.* 847, 157489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.157489>.
- Monteiro Dos Santos, D.A., Brito, J.F., Godoy, J.M., Artaxo, P., 2016. Ambient concentrations and insights on organic and elemental carbon dynamics in São Paulo, Brazil. *Atmos. Environ.* 144, 226–233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2016.08.081>.
- Munyanza, J., Hossain, M.F., Jia, Q., Duan, Y., Xiu, G., 2023. Space-time Characteristics of 16 PM_{2.5}-bound Phthalates (PAEs) in ambient air from Shanghai: profiles, sources, meteorological effects, and exposure risks. *Aerosol Air Qual. Res.* 23, 220465. <https://doi.org/10.4209/aaqr.220465>.
- Nadeem, H.R., Akhtar, S., Ismail, T., Sestili, P., Lorenzo, J.M., Ranjha, M.M.A.N., Jooste, L., Hano, C., Aadil, R.M., 2021. Heterocyclic aromatic amines in meat: formation, isolation, risk assessment, and inhibitory effect of plant extracts. *Foods* 10, 1466. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10071466>.
- Nagorka, R., Birmilli, W., Schulze, J., Koschorreck, J., 2022. Diverging trends of plasticizers (phthalates and non-phthalates) in indoor and freshwater environments—why? *Environ. Sci. Eur.* 34, 46. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-022-00620-4>.
- Noorian Najafabadi, S.A., Sugano, S., Bluyssen, P.M., 2022. Impact of carpets on indoor air quality. *Appl. Sci.* 12, 12989. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app122412989>.
- NRC, 1988. Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons: Mechanisms and metabolism.
- OECD, 2025. eChemPortal – Global portal to information on chemical substances [WWW Document]. OECD. (<https://www.echemportal.org>) (accessed 10.3.25).
- Palermo, C., Mentana, A., Tomaiuolo, M., Campaniello, M., Iammarino, M., Centonze, D., Zianni, R., 2024. Headspace solid-phase microextraction/gas chromatography–mass spectrometry and chemometric approach for the study of volatile profile in X-ray irradiated surface-ripened cheeses. *Foods* 13, 416. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13030416>.
- PCPC, 2025. INCI – international cosmetic ingredient dictionary & handbook [WWW Document. Pers. Care Prod. Council. (<https://www.personalcarecouncil.org/resources/inci/>) (accessed 10.2.25).
- Periyasamy, A.P., Tehrani-Bagha, A., 2022. A review on microplastic emission from textile materials and its reduction techniques. *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 199, 109901. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polydegradstab.2022.109901>.
- Pongpiachan, S., Wang, Q., Apiratikul, R., Tipmanee, D., Li, Y., Xing, L., Li, G., Han, Y., Cao, J., Macatangay, R.C., Poshyachinda, S., Aekakkarunroj, A., Hashmi, M. Z., 2022. An application of artificial neural network to evaluate the influence of weather conditions on the variation of PM_{2.5}-bound carbonaceous compositions and water-soluble ionic species. *Atmosphere* 13, 1042. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos13071042>.
- Pongpiachan, S., Tipmanee, D., Khumsup, C., Hirunyatrakul, P., Hashmi, M.Z., Poshyachinda, S., 2025b. Size-segregated analysis of PAHs in Urban air: source apportionment and health risk assessment in an Urban canal-adjacent environment. *PLOS One* 20, e0320405. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0320405>.
- Pongpiachan, S., Khruengsai, S., Sriphacho, T., Janta, Radshadaporn, Janta, Rungruang, Waewsak, J., Tipmanee, D., Poshyachinda, S., Pripdeevech, P., 2025a. Identifying PM_{2.5}-bound metal pollution sources in Southern Thailand using positive matrix factorization and principal component analysis. *Atmos. Environ.* X 26, 100337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aeoa.2025.100337>.
- Qadeer, A., Kirsten, K.L., Ajmal, Z., Jiang, X., Zhao, X., 2022. Alternative plasticizers as emerging global environmental and health threat: another regrettable substitution? *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 56, 1482–1488. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c08365>.
- Qin, M., Murphy, B.N., Isaacs, K.K., McDonald, B.C., Lu, Q., McKeen, S.A., Koval, L., Robinson, A.L., Efstathiou, C., Allen, C., Pye, H.O.T., 2020. Criteria pollutant impacts of volatile chemical products informed by near-field modelling. *Nat. Sustain.* 4, 129–137. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-00614-1>.
- Rádis-Baptista, G., 2023. Do synthetic fragrances in personal care and household products impact indoor air quality and pose health risks? *J. Xenobiotics* 13, 121–131. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jox13010010>.
- Rosen, E.M., Stevens, D.R., Ramos, A.M., McNell, E.E., Wood, M.E., Engel, S.M., Keil, A.P., Calafat, A.M., Botelho, J.C., Sinkovskaya, E., Przybylska, A., Saade, G., Abuhamad, A., Ferguson, K.K., 2024. Personal care product use patterns in association with phthalate and replacement biomarkers across pregnancy. *J. Expo. Sci. Environ. Epidemiol.* 34, 591–600. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41370-023-00627-w>.
- Rushdi, A.I., El-Mubarak, A.H., Lijotra, L., Al-Otaibi, M.T., Qurban, M.A., Al-Mutlaq, K.F., Simoneit, B.R.T., 2017. Characteristics of organic compounds in aerosol particulate matter from Dhahran city, Saudi Arabia. *Arab. J. Chem.* 10, S3532–S3547. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2014.03.001>.
- Ruzicková, J., Kucbel, M., Šýkorová, B., Pavlík, P., Raclavský, K., Sassmanová, V., 2017. Application of anthropogenic and geochemical markers in PM₁ particles for distinguishing emissions from coal combustion and transport. *DEStech Trans. Environ. Energy Earth Sci.* <https://doi.org/10.12783/dteees/ecds2016/5843>.
- Schauer, J.J., Kleeman, M.J., Cass, G.R., Simoneit, B.R.T., 1999. Measurement of emissions from air pollution Sources. 1. C₁ through C₂₉ organic compounds from meat charbroiling. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 33, 1566–1577. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es980076j>.
- Schwarz, J., Pokorná, P., Rychlík, Š., Škáchová, H., Vlček, O., Smolík, J., Ždímal, V., Hůnová, I., 2019. Assessment of air pollution origin based on year-long parallel measurement of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ at two suburban sites in Prague, Czech Republic. *Sci. Total Environ.* 664, 1107–1116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.01.426>.
- Sedghi, R., Shahbeik, H., Rastegari, H., Rafiee, S., Peng, W., Nizami, A.-S., Gupta, V.K., Chen, W.-H., Lam, S.S., Pan, J., Tabatabaei, M., Aghbashlo, M., 2022. Turning biodiesel glycerol into oxygenated fuel additives and their effects on the behavior of internal combustion engines: a comprehensive systematic review. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 167, 112805. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112805>.
- Seltzer, K.M., Murphy, B.N., Pennington, E.A., Allen, C., Talgo, K., Pye, H.O.T., 2022. Volatile chemical product enhancements to criteria pollutants in the United States. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 56, 6905–6913. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c04298>.
- Shinohara, N., Oguri, T., Takagi, M., Ueyama, J., Isobe, T., 2024. Evaluating the risk of phthalate and non-phthalate plasticizers in dust samples from 100 Japanese houses. *Environ. Int.* 183, 108399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2023.108399>.
- Simoneit, B.R.T., 1984. Organic matter of the troposphere—III. Characterization and sources of petroleum and pyrogenic residues in aerosols over the western united states. *Atmos. Environ.* 18, 51–67. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-6981\(84\)90228-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-6981(84)90228-2).
- Skiba, A., Styszko, K., Tobler, A., Casotto, R., Gorczyca, Z., Furman, P., Samek, L., Widel, D., Zimnoch, M., Kasper-Giebl, A., Slowik, J.G., Daellenbach, K.R., Prevot, A. S.H., Rózański, K., 2024. Source attribution of carbonaceous fraction of particulate matter in the urban atmosphere based on chemical and carbon isotope composition. *Sci. Rep.* 14, 7234. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-57829-x>.
- Song, J., Gkatzelis, G.I., Tillmann, R., Brüggemann, N., Leisner, T., Saathoff, H., 2024a. Characterization of biogenic volatile organic compounds and their oxidation products in a stressed spruce-dominated forest close to a biogas power plant. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 24, 13199–13217. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-24-13199-2024>.
- Song, G., Tao, J., Cui, L., Ma, S., Lv, Q., Chen, H., Liu, X., Yang, Y., Chen, D., 2024b. Non-phthalate ester plasticizers in airborne fine particles from Chinese cities: broad distributions and spatiotemporal trends. *Environ. Sci. Technol. Lett.* 11, 23–28. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.estlett.3c00728>.
- Sorvari, J., Hartikainen, S., 2021. Terpenes and fungal biomass in the nest mounds of *Formica aquilonia* wood ants. *Eur. J. Soil Biol.* 105, 103336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejsobi.2021.103336>.
- Spraul, M.H., Nitz, S., Drawert, F., 1991. Photochemical reactions of P-mentha-1,3,8-triene and structural related P-menthadienes. *Tetrahedron* 47, 3037–3044. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-4020\(01\)96033-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-4020(01)96033-8).
- Strantzali, D., Kostoglou, D., Perikleous, A., Zestas, M., Ornithopoulou, S., Dubois-Brissonnet, F., Giaouris, E., 2021. Comparative assessment of the disinfection effectiveness of thymol and benzalkonium chloride against adapted and non-adapted to thymol biofilm cells of a *Salmonella* Typhimurium epidemic phage type DT193 strain. *Food Control* 129, 108239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2021.108239>.
- U.S. EPA, 2007. Phthalates TEACH chemical summary.
- U.S. EPA, 2009. Exhaust emission profiles for EPA SPECIATE Database: Energy Policy Act (EPAct) low-level ethanol fuel blends and tier 2 lightduty vehicles.
- U.S. EPA, 2013. Guidance on choosing a sampling design for environmental data collection (QA/G-5S). EPA/240/R-02/005.
- U.S. EPA, 2025a. AP 42, Fifth Edition, volume I chapter 1: External combustion sources.
- U.S. EPA, 2025b. SPECIATE Version 5.4 – Specification Database and Documentation (mobile and coal combustion products).
- Vardoulakis, S., Giagloglou, E., Steinle, S., Davis, A., Sleuwehoeck, A., Galea, K.S., Dixon, K., Crawford, J.O., 2020. Indoor exposure to selected air pollutants in the home environment: a systematic review. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 17, 8972. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17238972>.

- Vera, P., Canellas, E., Su, Q.-Z., Mercado, D., Nerin, C., 2023. Migration of volatile substances from recycled high density polyethylene to milk products. *Food Packag. Shelf Life* 35, 101020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fpsl.2022.101020>.
- Waked, A., Favez, O., Alleman, L.Y., Piot, C., Petit, J.-E., Delaunay, T., Verlinden, E., Golly, B., Besombes, J.-L., Jaffrezo, J.-L., Leoz-Garziandia, E., 2014. Source apportionment of PM₁₀ in a north-western Europe regional urban background site (Lens, France) using positive matrix factorization and including primary biogenic emissions. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 14, 3325–3346. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-14-3325-2014>.
- Wang, R., Fang, K., Ren, Y., Song, Y., Zhang, K., Bukhari, M.N., 2019. Jetting performance of two lactam compounds in reactive dye solution. *J. Mol. Liq.* 294, 111668. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2019.111668>.
- Wang, S., Yuan, B., He, X., Cui, R., Song, X., Chen, Y., Wu, C., Wang, C., Huangfu, Y., Li, X., Wang, B., Shao, M., 2024. Emission characteristics of reactive organic gases from industrial volatile chemical products (VCPs) in China. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2024-380>.
- Wang, Y., Jiang, S., Chen, X., Liu, X., Li, N., Nie, Y., Lu, G., 2023. Comparison of developmental toxicity of benzophenone-3 and its metabolite benzophenone-8 in zebrafish. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 258, 106515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquatox.2023.106515>.
- Wernis, R.A., Kreisberg, N.M., Weber, R.J., Drozd, G.T., Goldstein, A.H., 2022. Source apportionment of VOCs, IVOCs and SVOCs by positive matrix factorization in suburban Livermore, California. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 22, 14987–15019. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-22-14987-2022>.
- Wiesinger, H., Wang, Z., Hellweg, S., 2021. Deep dive into plastic monomers, additives, and processing aids. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 55, 9339–9351. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c00976>.
- Yang, H., Ouyang, Y., Sun, Y., Wang, Z., Zhu, X., Tan, X., Wang, H., Hong, W., 2017. Facile synthesis of 1-(4-Bromophenyl)-1H-Tetrazol-5-Amine and related amide derivatives. *J. Chem. Res.* 41, 581–585. <https://doi.org/10.3184/174751917X15064232103128>.
- Yarwood, G., Tuite, K., 2024. Representing ozone formation from volatile chemical products (VCP) in carbon bond (CB) chemical mechanisms. *Atmosphere* 15, 178. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos15020178>.
- Zapletal, M., Cudlín, P., Khadka, C., Krůmal, K., Mikuška, P., Cigánková, H., Polásek, M., 2022. Characteristics and sources of PAHs, hopanes, and elements in PM10 aerosol in Tulsipur and Charikot (Nepal). *Water Air. Soil Pollut.* 233, 486. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-022-05953-7>.
- Zhou, L., Liang, Z., Qin, Y., Chan, C.K., 2024. Evaporation-induced transformations in volatile chemical product-derived secondary organic aerosols: browning effects and alterations in oxidative reactivity. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 58, 11105–11117. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.4c02316>.